

**THE EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION ON STUDENTS'
ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS AT THE TSHWANE UNIVERSITY OF
TECHNOLOGY**

by

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Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree

**MAGISTER TECHNOLOGIAE: ENTREPRENEURSHIP
(STRUCTURED)**

in the

Department of Management and Entrepreneurship

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

TSHWANE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

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June 2021

DECLARATION AND COPYRIGHT

I hereby declare that this dissertation/thesis submitted for the degree M Tech: Entrepreneurship at the Tshwane University of Technology is my own work and has not previously been submitted to any other institution of higher education. I further declare that all sources cited or quoted are indicated and acknowledged by means of a comprehensive list of references.

Simon Thabo Mahlaole

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to Jesus Christ, my Lord and saviour, whose faith in me has always strengthened me even in my darkest hour. I would also like to dedicate this thesis to my late father, Jerry Hlengane Mahlaole, who always had confidence in me and offered me encouragement and support in all my endeavours.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Firstly, I would like to thank my Lord and saviour, Jesus Christ. Thank you, Lord. Without you, I would have never been able to finish this programme in due time. Secondly, I would like to thank my fiancée, Nyakallo Agnes Matlali, for always believing in me and pushing me to keep going even when all I wanted to do was give up. I literally do not know what I would do without you. You are the dock to my boat, my lighthouse in the storm, you are my whole heart, always.

Thirdly, I would like to express my sincere gratitude and appreciation to my supervisor, Dr Mmakgabo Justice Malebana, for his time, guidance and extraordinary patience with me. Thank you for being very supportive and providing me with a lot of advice, direction, useful insights and invaluable feedback in relation to this masters' dissertation. Kea leboga.

Fourthly, I would like to express my special thanks to Ms Princess Ramokolo for her assistance with statistical analysis and data preparation, and Ms Susanna Elizabeth Louw for her help with language editing.

Fifthly, to my sponsors, GCRA and service SETA. Thank you for providing me with the necessary funds and scholarships to further my studies at the Tshwane University of Technology. None of this would have been possible without your constant financial support.

Last, but not least, I would like to thank my friends Sibusiso Prince Twala, Mpho Wendy Mathebula, Russel Mnisi, Sizo Bongani Masinga and Thapelo Maluleke, for all the support and motivation, as well as my mother, Regina Manzana, for supporting my dreams and being my source of inspiration. Also, this mini-dissertation would not have been completed without the respondents who took part in this study. I extend my genuine recognition to all of you.

I love you all.

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intentions at the Tshwane University of Technology using the theory of planned behaviour. The study explored the influence of entrepreneurship education, perceived effects of entrepreneurship education, perceived behavioural control, subjective norms and attitude towards behaviour on entrepreneurial intentions. A total of 301 first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students completed the online survey questionnaire. The study's conceptual model was tested using partial least-squares structural equation modeling in RStudio. Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS 26 were used for descriptive statistics.

The findings generated from the PLS-SEM model showed that entrepreneurship education had a statistically significant influence on entrepreneurial intentions and perceived behavioural control. Moreover, the results further revealed that perceived behavioural control partially mediated the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions. Entrepreneurship education did not have a statistically significant relationship with subjective norms and attitude towards behaviour.

Perceived effects of entrepreneurship education had a statistically significant effect on perceived behavioural control, subjective norms and attitude towards behaviour, and an insignificant direct effect on entrepreneurial intentions. The relationship between entrepreneurial intentions and perceived effects of entrepreneurship education was fully mediated by perceived behavioural control, subjective norms and attitude towards behaviour. The findings further revealed that perceived behavioural control, subjective norms, and attitude towards behaviour had a statistically significant influence on entrepreneurial intentions. This study's findings add to the theory of planned behaviour as well as the field of entrepreneurship education.

Future research should consider combining the entrepreneurial event model with the theory of planned behaviour and evaluate the influence that entrepreneurship education has on the entrepreneurial intentions of students in South Africa.

Keywords:

Perceived effects of entrepreneurship education; theory of planned behaviour; entrepreneurial knowledge; entrepreneurship education; subjective norms; work experience; perceived behavioural control; attitude towards behaviour; Tshwane University of Technology; entrepreneurial intentions.

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS

ATB	Attitude towards behaviour (Entrepreneurship behaviour)
AVE	Average variance extracted
DME	Department of Management and Entrepreneurship
EE	Entrepreneurship education
EI	Entrepreneurial Intention(s)
EIQ	Entrepreneurial Intentions Questionnaire
FCRE	Faculty Committee for Research Ethics
PD	Perceived desirability
PBC	Perceived behavioural control
PEE	Perceived effects of entrepreneurship education
PF	Perceived desirability
PLS	Partial least squares
PTA	Propensity to act
REC	Research Ethics Committee
EEM	Entrepreneurial event model
SA	South Africa
SEM	Structural equation modelling
SN	Subjective norms
SPSS	Statistical Product and Service Solutions
TPB	Theory of planned behaviour
TUT	Tshwane University of Technology
GEM	Global Entrepreneurship Monitor

CHAPTER 1: BACKGROUND

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The concept of entrepreneurship has become an issue of importance due to the constant and increasing economic problems particularly related to unemployment (García-Rodríguez, Gutiérrez-Taño & Ruiz-Rosa, 2017:164). According to Shane and Venkataraman (2000:218), entrepreneurship involves examining “how by whom, and with what effects opportunities to create future goods and services are discovered, evaluated and exploited.” In recent times, academics, specialists and policymakers have regarded entrepreneurship as an important catalyst of economic growth, development and productivity (Tijani, 2017:16; De Wit & De Kok, 2014:283). Byun, Sung, Park and Choi (2018:1) mentioned that most tertiary institutions currently providing entrepreneurial training believe that fostering entrepreneurship education (EE) can lead to policy support, economic growth and job creation. Hence, university education, particularly in African developing countries, no longer carries an assurance of guaranteed employment (Mwiya, Wang, Shikaputa, Kaulungombe & Kayekesi, 2017:593).

South Africa (SA) is currently experiencing a youth unemployment crisis (Statistics South Africa, 2020:15). The 2017/2018 Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) report confirms the low level of entrepreneurship activity in SA compared to other participating countries (Global Entrepreneurship Research Association, 2018:13). In the 2017 GEM report, Herrington, Kew and Mwangi (2017:7) indicated that the percentage of 18 to 24-year-olds in SA involved in early-stage entrepreneurial activity is considerably lower than the average for Africa, which at 11 percent is almost double the South African figure. A high unemployment rate clearly indicates that the general activity of South Africans with regard to entrepreneurship is low compared to other countries (Chimucheka, 2014:404). With SA's youth unemployment rate now at 61.3%, this is cause for concern (Statistics South Africa, 2020:15).

Moses, Olokundun, Akinbode, Agboola and Inelo (2016:645) stated that the value of EE for entrepreneurship cannot be overemphasised due to the advantages it holds for employment creation and economic growth. Jones and English (2004:416) as quoted

by Kaltenecker, Hoerndlein and Hess (2015:2) characterised “EE as the process of providing individuals with the ability to recognise commercial opportunities and the insight, self-esteem, knowledge and skills to act on them.” Olokundun, Ibadunni, Peter, Amaihian and Ogbari (2017:2) reported that EE aims to provide people with skills needed to identify opportunities, mobilise resources, set up and manage enterprises. Ayou, Auka and Kibas (2017:86) reiterated that EE contributes to entrepreneurial intentions (EI) by promoting right thinking and making them aware of career opportunities as an entrepreneur and providing relevant business skills. Hien and Beri (2018:3) stated that “EE is important to the development of entrepreneurial capabilities. Individuals who receive basic EE are more likely to engage in entrepreneurship.” EI are “self-acknowledged conviction by a person that they intend to set up a new business venture and consciously plan to do so at some point in the future.” (Thompson 2009:676).

Education is essential, and EE can play an important role in the development of entrepreneurship culture in SA (Chimucheka, 2014:406). Investigating the effects of EE could support the efforts to encourage entrepreneurship in SA. Additionally, the research findings may help policymakers determine the effectiveness of EE in influencing students’ intentions to become entrepreneurs. Growing the number of individuals with the abilities and skills needed to start an enterprise would be vital for the country’s economic growth and employment creation challenges. This research examines, based on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), the effects of EE on the intentions of students at the Tshwane University of Technology (TUT) to start a business.

1.2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The TPB, its application in the field of entrepreneurship, and empirical proof of its application are all discussed in this section.

The TPB was founded on Ajzen and Fishbein’s theory of reasoned action, which they established in 1980 (Ajzen, 2012:438). The TPB has evolved into a critical model for comprehension, prediction, and altering people’s social behaviour (Ajzen, 2012:438). The TPB states that attitudes towards behaviour (entrepreneurship behaviour) (ATB),

subjective norms (SN), and perceived behavioural control (PBC) all influence intentions to set up a business (Ajzen, 2012:445; 2011:1117). Ajzen (2006:1) states that:

“In their respective aggregates, behavioural beliefs produce a favourable or unfavourable attitude toward the behaviour; normative beliefs result in perceived social pressure or subjective norm; and control beliefs give rise to perceived behavioural control. In combination, attitude toward the behaviour, subjective norm, and perception of behavioural control lead to the formation of a behavioural intention.”

The TPB has demonstrated its efficiency as a basis for designing and evaluating interventions of various kinds, which include the EI of university students (Ubierna, Arranz & Fdez de Arroyabe, 2014:51). For instance, Tarek (2017:76) utilised the TPB to explore the EI of final-year university students within the Tunisian economy. His findings demonstrated that all of the TPB's antecedents were statistically significantly related to EI. In SA, Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:89) conducted a study on the EI of graduates in rural areas. Their findings supported the TPB in relation to PBC and ATB, but not in terms of SN. Similarly, Nieuwenhuizen and Swanepoel (2015:4) compared the ability of the TPB to predict the EI of students in SA and Poland. Their findings revealed that personal attitude and PBC had a positive effect on intentions, but not in relation to SN. Galvão, Marques and Marques (2018:728) utilised the TPB to test EI amongst students' and professionals within vocational training programmes. Their findings pointed out a moderate effect of the TPB model concerning personal attitude and PBC over EI, but they found that normative beliefs had no direct effect on EI. Shah and Soomro (2017:841) applied the TPB model on public sector university scholars of Pakistan and found that ATB, in addition to PBC, had a positive relationship with EI. Despite the predictive nature of the TPB, previous research has shown that the effect of PBC, SN and ATB differs from one group to the other.

Pulka, Aminu and Rikwentishe (2015:154) used the TPB model to examine the effects of EE on university students' attitude and EI. Their results revealed a positive relationship between EE and students' intentions to become entrepreneurs. Ajike, Kelechi, Hamed, Onyia, and Kwarbai (2015:118) employed the TPB to examine the

impact of EE on the EI of Nigerian tertiary education students. They found that SN, ATB and PBC mediated the link between EE and EI. The TPB was also used by Ebewo, Rugimbana, and Shambare (2017:276) to analyse the influence of EE on students' EI. Their results indicated that EE positively influenced students' intentions to become entrepreneurs. Furthermore, their results provided evidence that PBC, ATE and SN are direct antecedents of EI. Their findings were supported by those of Norliana, Fakhrul Anwar, Wan Norhayate, Norfadzilah and Asyraf (2018:130), with specific reference to the positive relationship between EE and EI. According to the literature, EE has been a consistent predictor of EI.

1.3 RESEARCH PROBLEM

A high youth unemployment rate negatively affects economic growth and productivity, which cannot be ignored. According to Herrington, Kew, and Mwangi (2017:7), the percentage of young people in SA engaged in early-stage entrepreneurship is significantly lower than the African average. This has been a cause for concern. There is a risk that qualified and talented people will be lost because a large number of graduates cannot find work and use their knowledge and skills to innovate and contribute to economic growth. High youth unemployment not only leads to lower productivity, it raises the country's economic costs because more money must be spent on education and less money is received through taxes. However, most tertiary institutions that provide entrepreneurial training believe that fostering EE can lead to policy support, economic growth and employment creation. As a result, It is critical to investigate the degree to which EE influences EI amongst TUT students.

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research objectives, hypotheses, and proposed research model are all outlined in this section of the study.

1.4.1 Primary objective

The primary objective of this research was to evaluate the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT.

1.4.2 Secondary objectives

The following are the secondary objectives of this research:

- To assess if EE has a significant impact on students' EI.
- To determine the impact of EE on students' ATB.
- To establish the impact of EE on students' SN.
- To assess the impact EE has on students' PBC.

1.4.3 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated based on the objectives of the study:

H₀₁: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' EI.

H₁: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' EI.

H₀₂: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.

H₂: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.

H₀₃: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' SN.

H₃: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' SN.

H₀₄: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.

H₄: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.

1.4.4 Research model

The proposed research model shown below in Figure 1.1 was drawn from Ajzen's (2012:438) TPB, which was modified to accommodate the possible role that EE and its perceived effects play in stimulating students' EI. The model illustrates the variables on which this study was based and shows the relationship between these variables. Based on the literature review, EE and perceived effects of entrepreneurship education (PEE) were defined as the independent variables. PBC, SN and ATB were regarded as the mediating variables, while EI was considered as the dependent

variable. The proposed model suggests that the two independent variables, namely, EE and PEE, have an effect on EI, mediated by PBC, SN and ATB.

Figure 1.1: Proposed research model

Source: Researcher's own compilation, adapted from Ajzen (2012:438)

1.5 METHODOLOGY

1.5.1 Research design

To investigate the study's research objectives, a quantitative research approach was employed. Quantitative research was chosen because it allows for the quantification of behaviour, opinions, attitudes, and other variables, as well as the generalization of findings across a larger population. In this study, a cross-sectional descriptive research survey design was used. Leedy and Ormrod (2015:154) defined descriptive research design as "a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behaviour of a subject without influencing it in any way." Creswell (2012) as quoted by

Belay (2016:220) defined survey research designs as “procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to the entire population to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviours or characteristics of the population.” A cross-sectional study is defined as “an observational research type that analyses data of variables collected at one given point of time across a sample population” (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015:158).

1.5.2 Population and sampling

According to Cooper and Schindler (2014:338), “a population is the total collection of elements about which we wish to make some inferences.” The population of this study consisted of 1 003 first, second and third year entrepreneurship students registered in 2020 with the Department of Management and Entrepreneurship (DME) in the Faculty of Management Sciences at TUT, identified through the institution’s registrar directorate.

The basic idea of sampling, according to Cooper and Schindler (2014:338), involves selecting elements in a population that we can use to draw conclusions about the entire population. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016:274) reported that, when a researcher cannot include all population members in a research, a sample that is representative of the population is taken in order to accurately generalise the results. Cooper and Schindler (2014:84) indicated that a sample is “a portion of the target population which must be carefully selected to represent that population.” Hence, with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error, 278 first, second, and third-year entrepreneurship students at TUT were recommended as the sample size for this study.

First, second and third-year entrepreneurship students were chosen because the entrepreneurship course focuses on providing students with entrepreneurial skills and expertise required to establish and develop a new business venture from the first year of study all the way through to the last year of study. Moreover, entrepreneurship students are more likely to look for employment or start their own businesses during the course or soon after graduation. This study utilised a convenience sampling method. Leedy and Ormrod (2015:182) defined convenience sampling as “a non-

probability sampling method where the sample is taken from a group of people easy to contact or to reach.” This sampling method was used because entrepreneurship students were well suited for investigating the relationships among the key variables of this study and were readily accessible.

1.5.3 Data collection

Primary data was gathered to assess the degree upon which EE impacts EI among TUT students. Primary data was gathered by making use of an online survey, using an existing Entrepreneurial Intentions Questionnaire (EIQ) adopted without any modifications from Liñán and Chen (2009:612), Malebana (2012:389) and Rengiah (2013:285). The information acquired through the online survey questionnaire was employed to evaluate the effects which EE has on students' EI at TUT.

1.5.4 Data analysis

Data was analysed using analytical methods such as descriptive statistics and inferential multivariate statistics. Partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) was used to establish the reliability and validity of the questionnaire and test study hypotheses. Sanchez (2013:4) defined SEM as a statistical analysis technique used to analyse structural relationships between latent variables. PLS is a broad concept for analysing block and variables, where you take into account some previous knowledge of the phenomenon under analysis and assume that each block of variables plays a role of a theoretical concept represented by the latent variables (Sanchez, 2013:4). The Sobel test was used for mediation analysis. Koopman, Howe and Hollenback (2014:241) recommended using the Sobel test over bootstrapping to determine the strength and significance of the p -value derived from the study variables in mediation analysis.

This method was used because “PLS-SEM is a SEM method that can model measurement error, can be used to validate measurement models, works well with small sample sizes, and provides significance tests regarding the null hypotheses of path coefficients, is appropriate for exploratory, model building research” (Ravand & Baghaei, 2016:3). Therefore, it was suitable for analysing the relationship between EE

and this study's key variables. The data was captured via a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analysed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) v26 and RStudio.

1.5.5 Reliability and Validity

Reliability relates to “the consistency of a measure and validity is defined as the extent to which a concept is accurately measured in a quantitative study” (Heale & Twycross, 2015:66). Putka and Sackett (2010:9) indicated that “reliability and validity are concepts that provide the scientific foundation upon which we construct and evaluate predictor and criterion measures of interest.” The existing literature was consulted to allow the use of a validated questionnaire with no modifications. To ensure validity and reliability of the research instrument, the adopted questionnaire was piloted to similar respondents (Faculty of Management Science Students) beforehand to determine the clarity of items and consistency of the responses to confirm validity (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011:53). Moreover, convergent validity was used to evaluate how the scale of a concept was related to other variables and other measures of the same construct (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2017:112). To establish if the model's constructs were highly correlated with each other, discriminant validity was used (Hair *et al.*, 2017:115). Since the quality of the study relied on accurately measuring constructs under study, the Dillion-Goldstein’s rho and Cronbach’s alpha were used to measure the composite reliability of the questionnaire.

1.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study was carried out in line with the ethical guidelines specified by the TUT Research Ethics Committee (REC). Ethical clearance was sourced from the Faculty Committee of Research Ethics (FCRE) and the institution’s REC. The following ethical guidelines were followed as set out by TUT:

- Respondents were advised about the nature of the questionnaire, aim and importance of the study being conducted, their role in the study, how the information they provided will be used, and their voluntary consent to participate in the study.

- Ethical clearance was attained through the FCRE and the institution's REC before the research instrument was distributed to students.
- The anonymity and the confidentiality of the respondents were protected during the survey process. All information collected was considered group data and was not disclosed to anyone.
- The data collected during the research process will be stored for at least five years. Respondents' dignity and personality were always respected, and they were not subjected to shame or inappropriate behaviour.

1.7 CHAPTER OUTLINE

The following is an overview of the report:

Chapter 1: Introduction – The introductory chapter provides the basis for this research. It defines the context for this study and indicates the significance of the selected concept. To contextualise the study, the theoretical background, research problem, study objectives, research model and the research methodology are discussed within this chapter.

Chapter 2: Literature review – This chapter examines the literature needed to develop a theoretical basis for answering the research questions. It concentrates on articles, thesis and peer-reviewed journal publications etc. in the subject field.

Chapter 3: Research methodology – The study methods and techniques used, such as sampling, the measurement instrument, data collection and data analysis are all discussed in depth.

Chapter 4: Findings – This chapter presents and discusses the results of this research.

Chapter 5: Conclusions and recommendations – The results are compared to those of previous studies in this chapter. The study's limitations are also discussed, as well as recommendations for future studies.

1.8 CHAPTER SUMMARY

Within this chapter, the research problem, study objectives, study hypotheses and research model were introduced. Moreover, the introduction and theoretical background justifying this research were presented. Lastly, the methodology of the study, ethical concerns, and chapter outline were also explained. The following chapter gives a detailed literature review about the key concepts of this study.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter reviews the literature that formed the theoretical basis for achieving the research objectives. An emphasis was placed on reviewing articles, thesis and peer-reviewed journal publications in the current field of the impact of EE and the TPB to give a theoretical framework for measuring EI. The chapter starts with a discussion on the concept of entrepreneurship, EE and EI. The literature review defines the state of research on the effects of educational studies on entrepreneurship. Subsequently, the relationship between EE and EI is determined through the TPB.

2.2 THE CONCEPT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Entrepreneurship examines “how, by whom, and with what effects opportunities to create future goods and services are discovered, evaluated and exploited” (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000:218). It dates all the way back to the 17th century (Portales, 2019:51) and is derived from the French term ‘entre’ which stands for ‘between’ and “prendre” which implies “to take” (Tunc & Alkan, 2019:40). The concept of entrepreneurship has crossed sectors and is increasingly widespread in the education and non-profit sectors (Mwatsika, Kambewa & Chiwaula, 2018:452). Entrepreneurship is a vital source of economic growth and an important factor in the social and economic well-being of society (Ahmed, Chandran, Klobas, Liñán & Kokkalis, 2020:327).

Different scholars, like Bruyat and Julien (2001:165), Shane and Venkataraman (2000:219) and Drucker (1985:141) characterised entrepreneurship from a variety of perspectives; nevertheless, the different concepts are generally an impression of the analyst’s field of specialisation. For instance, Muñoz and Cohen (2018:301) described “entrepreneurship as a solution to, rather than a cause of, environmental degradation and social inequality.” Hisrich, Peters and Shepherd (2009) as quoted by Ebewo, Rugimbana & Shambare (2017:279) labelled entrepreneurship as “the process of creating something new with value by allocating the necessary time and effort assuming the accompanying financial, physical and social risk, receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence.” Entrepreneurship

is a long-term behavioural process that takes place over time (Liguori, Winker, Vanevenhoven, Winkel & James, 2020:312). EI is an important concept in better understanding why individuals participate in the entrepreneurship process (Ajzen, 2011:1113). Why people become entrepreneurs is a major research topic (Hui-Chen, Kuen-Hung & Chen-Yi, 2014:728). Dahalan, Jaafar and Rosdi (2015:01008) mentioned that “entrepreneurship requires opportunities that can lead to individual actions; therefore, intentions can be regarded as a catalyst to action.”

2.2.1 Entrepreneurial process

Baron and Shane (2008:5) as cited by Mothibi (2018:12) denoted “entrepreneurship, as an activity carried out by specific individuals, involving the key actions like identifying an opportunity that is potentially valuable in the sense that it can be exploited in practical business terms and yield sustainable profits.” Launching a new business requires a great deal of time and effort to examine the feasibility of an idea before putting it into action (Leach & Melicher, 2014:6). The entrepreneurial process consists of factors such as identifying an opportunity, gathering resources and assembling an entrepreneurial team (Timmons & Spinelli, 2009:158). These three driving factors of the entrepreneurial process are interlinked, with any change in one factor affecting the other two (Yeh & Chang, 2018:325). Figure 2.1 below illustrates a graphical demonstration of the entrepreneurial process.

Figure 2.1: The Timmons model of the entrepreneurial process

Source: Timmons and Spinelli (2009:110)

2.2.1.1 Opportunity

The entrepreneurial process, according to Yeh and Chang (2018:326), begins with an opportunity that is far larger than the team's aptitude or capability, or the initial resources available to the team. "Opportunities are more important than the talent or ability of entrepreneur and the team because a right opportunity exploited ensures long term success of the organisation" (Moises, 2012:2 as quoted by Yeh & Chang, 2018:326). Entrepreneurial opportunity, according to Rubleske and Berente (2017:122), is a dynamic and unfolding experience that an entrepreneur perceives as an overall market need that can be exploited for financial and social gain.

A good idea, according to Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2014:102), does not always translate into a great opportunity. To see if a business idea can turn into a profitable opportunity, characterised by timely quality, sustainability and attractiveness, the entrepreneur must follow a strategy to evaluate and select the opportunity (Nieman & Nieuwenhuizen, 2014:103). An entrepreneur can achieve this by being creative and innovative, in other words, by coming up with new and unique ideas and bringing

something better to market (Nieman & Nieuwenhuizen, 2014:111). This process can aid entrepreneurs to establish whether their business ideas are feasible (Nieman & Nieuwenhuizen, 2014:103). Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2014:113) further stated that, once an entrepreneur has become accustomed to the process of opportunity screening and evaluation, it becomes second nature to them, and they can see opportunities in nearly every action and occurrence in their daily lives.

2.2.1.2 Resources

Entrepreneurial resources are the things that an entrepreneur requires to pursue a business opportunity (Nieman & Nieuwenhuizen, 2014:142). They are specific resources required by a new business to create value, as well as the necessary condition for the foundation and operation of a new business (Huang, 2016:4). Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2014:142) mentioned that there are four types of resources entrepreneurs need to exploit opportunities, namely, financial, informational, physical and human resources. Table 2.1 presents a summary of those resources.

Table 2.1: Summary of entrepreneurial resources

Resource type	Description
Financial resources	The money a new business needs to have available in the form of cash, liquid securities and credit line. Before starting a new business, an entrepreneur needs to have sufficient financial resources to efficiently run the business.
Informational resources	Resources such as knowledge of a specific area of communication networks that the entrepreneur can connect to or can advertise with, or that can provide other benefits necessary for business development. Entrepreneurs require two types of information resources, namely, information about their prospective business's external environment and information about the internal workings of the business.

Physical resources	Tangible items which are used for the running of a business. Tangible resources include, among others, access to capital and location.
Human resources	The personnel a new business needs to operate and manage resources related to employees.

Source: Adapted from Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2014:142-143)

One of the misinterpretations among novice entrepreneurs, according to the Timmons model, is that in order to be effective in starting a company, one must first have all of the resources in place (Ghee, 2018:513). However, focusing on money is a common blunder that can impede the entire entrepreneurial process (Ghee, 2018:513).

2.2.1.3 Team

A well-equipped entrepreneur must be capable of putting together the best skilled team after recognising an opportunity and collecting all the necessary resources (Moises, 2012:3). The Timmons model of the entrepreneurial process states that, a well-formed team can lead to great success, while a poorly-formed team can squander great ideas, which is disastrous for any type of business (Ghee, 2018:514). Even with all of the resources at their disposal, only a strong team can unlock the full potential of any opportunity and manage the associated risks (Moises, 2012:3).

2.3 THE CONCEPT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS

The empirical research of EI was first championed by Shapero and Sokol, and Ajzen, with seminal research articles produced in 1982, 1984, 1985 and 1991 (Martin, Santos & Silveira, 2019:48). Since then, several studies examining the antecedents of EI have emerged based on the psychological concepts and sociological concepts (Kolvereid, 2016:101; Pfeifer, Šarlija, & Zekić Sušac, 2016:102; Ibrahim & Mas'ud, 2016:225; Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000:411; Krueger & Carsrud, 1993:315) The literature focusing on EI studies exhibit a series of models that seek to explain the relationship between the antecedents of EI and EI (Martin, Santos & Silveira, 2019:48; Kolvereid, 2016:101; Kautonen, Van Gelderen & Fink, 2015:655; Liñán & Fayolle, 2015:907;

Schlaegel & Koenig, 2014:291). These models focus on two main lines – the TBP, by Ajzen (2012:438; 1991:179), and the entrepreneurial event model (EEM), by Shapero and Sokol (1982:72) and Shapero (1984:21). Liñán and Fayolle (2015:907) alluded that the measurement of the TPB and EI carried out by Liñán and Chen (2009:593) increased the importance of the literature on the theme of EI.

2.4 THE ROLE AND VALUE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL PROCESS

The role of EE in the entrepreneurial process is discussed in this section. The relationship between EE and entrepreneurial activities is also discussed.

2.4.1 Entrepreneurship education

EE is “an educational program that is focused on impacting students with issues on entrepreneurship” (Ajike *et al.*, 2015:128). Dakung, Orobia, Munene and Balunywa (2017:298) stated that “EE refers to the scope of curricular, lectures or courses that provides students with entrepreneurial competencies, skills and knowledge in pursuing entrepreneurial career.” EE plays a critical role in equipping people with the necessary skills and intellectual capacity to launch their own business (Maina, 2014:94). Wahidmurni, Indah, Alfiana and Abdussakir (2020:2) mentioned that EE is alleged to be a solution that can be used to overcome unemployment in many countries. This has been proven by the many EE courses offered in various university study programmes globally (Wahidmurni *et al.*, 2020:2). Karimi, Biemans, Lans, Aazami and Mulder (2016a:221) stated that in entrepreneurial courses, students develop a higher degree of divergence in thinking and skills to produce more and more innovative business ideas than the control group. Hien and Beri (2018:3) stated that:

“EE is important to the development of entrepreneurial capabilities. Individuals who receive basic EE are more likely to engage in entrepreneurship. EE is an important method of encouraging entrepreneurship, because it triggers feelings of independence and self-confidence, enables the recognition of alternative career options, broadens individuals’ horizons by enabling them to perceive more

opportunities and provides the knowledge for individuals to use in developing new business opportunities.”

2.4.2 The importance of entrepreneurship education in the start-up process

According to Fayolle (2013:693), EE is becoming increasingly popular in business schools, engineering schools and universities. Alanazi (2018:6) mentioned that “EE programs are no longer only small programs for elective courses in undergraduate or graduate schools; they have become a doctorate category at international universities.” Fayolle (2013:698) also mentioned that EE research and practices could assist in addressing key issues faced by entrepreneurs in various situations and show how entrepreneurs can learn to address the problems they face. On the other hand, Marques and Albuquerque (2012:56) indicated that EE should reveal the effectiveness and dynamic potential of individuals and stimulate their potential to start a business. Tiwari, Bhat, Tikaria and Saha (2019:13) argued that universities should organise more activities and programmes related to entrepreneurship to enhance students’ interests in entrepreneurial activities. Solomon (2007:169) stated that:

“If EE is to produce entrepreneurial founders capable of generating real enterprise growth and wealth, the challenge to educators will be to craft courses, programs and major fields of study that meet the rigors of academia while keeping a reality-based focus and entrepreneurial climate in the learning experience environment.”

In other words, educators can strengthen the effects of EE on students’ EI by using experiential learning methods. Hence, EE courses are designed to raise students’ awareness of entrepreneurship, prepare them as beginners while teaching them the essential skills required to start a business (Aloulou, 2017:9). Osuala (2010) as spelt out by Maina (2014:92) outlined the objectives of EE as follows:

- Offer young people meaningful training that can make them independent and motivate them to strive for independence.

- Provide students with training and support they need to advance their careers in small and medium-sized businesses.
- Provide students with learning capabilities which will allow them to meet society's human needs.
- Provide appropriate risk management instructions to students so that they can come up with easy and effective solutions to issues involving uncertainty.
- Provide opportunities for small and medium-sized business to hire qualified graduates who are trained and equipped with skills required for the successful operation of a company.

Centred on EE's aforementioned roles, a conclusion can be drawn that EE, when implemented properly, will produce quality graduates who will be able to create jobs and reduce the element of poverty in the society (Maina, 2014:93). Dakung *et al.* (2017:298) mentioned that a key part of EE is providing students with thorough knowledge of how to start a business. Furthermore, most empirical studies show that EE can be taught and that EE can be seen as one of the key tools in developing ATB, PBC, SN and EI. (Hien & Beri, 2018:3; Ayou, Auka & Kibas, 2017:86; Karimi *et al.*, 2016a:217; Ajike *et al.*, 2015:119; Pulka, Aminu & Rikwentishe, 2015:150). Figure 2.1 below shows the role of EE in the entrepreneurial process as illustrated by Liñán (2007:241).

Figure 2.2: Role of entrepreneurship education in the entrepreneurial process

Source: Liñán (2007:241)

According to Liñán (2007:240), “development of [EI] could allegedly be considered as the first element to be addressed” in the entrepreneurial process. Hence examining the effect of EE on students’ EI is of critical importance and the focal point of this study. Liñán (2007:240) indicated that “transmitting the important role entrepreneurs play in economic growth and development would help improve participants’ valuation of entrepreneurship.” Liñán (2007:241-242) further indicated that, after emphasising the significance of the entrepreneur within the economy, developing students’ opportunity recognition skills and enhancing their creativity must follow suit. Therefore, lecturers should teach students to be creative thinkers and identify opportunities within the business environment. Liñán (2007:242) further mentioned that students should be paired with a mentor (entrepreneur) who “considers the student as a kind of adviser, letting him/her take part in all business decisions made by the entrepreneur.” After the opportunities have been identified, the planning needed to start a new firm is the succeeding step. Once the business has been created, it is up to the entrepreneur (student) to maintain and sustain the business for it to hopefully grow.

2.4.3 The link between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial activity

Entrepreneurial activity is defined as an enterprising human action aimed at creating or expanding economic activity by identifying and exploiting new products, processes, or markets in order to generate value (Ahmad & Seymour, 2008:14). It is a complex process that involves the start of new firms, the expansion of existing companies and the restructuring or shutdown of failed businesses (Korent, Vuković & Brčić, 2015:940). Meyer and Meyer (2017:431) stated that researchers and policymakers have acknowledged entrepreneurial activity as a critical factor in a country's economic development and stability. On the other hand, EE involves the teaching and learning of activities that focus on instilling students' behaviours and mind-sets with the entrepreneurial knowledge, skills and capabilities needed to pursue entrepreneurial careers (Fabeil, 2019:1065). According to Walter and Block (2016:219), EE can make starting a business easier or more desirable because business is based on the belief that seizing a particular opportunity is possible and desirable. The more entrepreneurial knowledge and motivation a person has from EE, the more likely he or she will be able to overcome regulatory barriers and engage in entrepreneurial behaviour (Walter & Block, 2016:219).

Shirokova, Tsukanova and Morris (2018:106-107) substantiated that access to EE for many factors, can be positively related to the variety of entrepreneurial activities undertaken by students. For example:

- EE assists in the acquisition of applicable concepts, skills, resources, and frameworks for venture creation.
- EE teaches how to communicate business concepts to a specific market and how to expand the reach of entrepreneurial activities.

EE stimulates entrepreneurial activity (Walter & Block, 2016:216). Raposo and Do Paço (2011:144) mentioned that, even though the link between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial activity is not conclusive, there are significant empirical findings suggesting the linkage. Shirokova, Tsukanova and Morris (2018:106-122)

stated that participating in EE can make a difference, particularly when engaging in entrepreneurial activities that are more inclusive and include experiential elements. Government and policymakers can indirectly play an active role in increasing entrepreneurial activity among students (entrepreneurs) – even more so if they work together with higher education institutions to create entrepreneurial opportunities for the youth (Hamilton & Mostert, 2019:165).

Oo, Sahaym, Juasrikul and Lee (2018:411) pointed out that EE's findings are more influential in fostering entrepreneurial activity in nations which value more individualism, less ambiguity avoidance, and higher levels of masculinity. Their findings strongly supported the notion that entrepreneurship can be taught and that policymakers may feel more secure about investing in EE (Oo *et al.*, 2018:416). To be more precise, EE can contribute to the development of entrepreneurial abilities by providing information regarding how to start a business and encouraging entrepreneurial initiatives while developing entrepreneurial mind-sets, hence policymakers should be more confident in investing in EE (Oo *et al.*, 2018:416).

2.5 MODELS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS

The TPB and the EEM are two widely used and well-known entrepreneurial models. This section of the study focuses on the EEM, whereas the TPB is rigorously discussed in section 2.5.3.

2.5.1 Shapero and Sokol's entrepreneurial event model

The EEM was established by Shapero and Sokol in 1982 to define the interaction of cultural and social factors that can lead one to start one's own business (Shapero & Sokol, 1982:72). According to the EEM, two prerequisites must be met prior to actually starting a business. To begin, an individual must believe that the idea of starting a new business is plausible, such that, it is both appealing and achievable. Second, starting a business is triggered by some type of displacement event, which could be neutral, negative, or positive (Davids, 2017:16-17). Graduation from university is an example of a neutral event. Losing a job or getting divorced are examples of negative events. Positive events, on the other hand, could also include receiving an inherited wealth or

venture capital from an investor (Davids, 2017:17). EI is derived from perceived feasibility (PF), perceived desirability (PD) and propensity to act (PTA) upon opportunities (Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000:417). Each predictor of the model is discussed below.

Figure 2.3: Entrepreneurial event model

Source: Krueger, Reilly and Carsrud (2000:418)

The EEM consists of three types of perceptions:

- PD refers to “the personal attractiveness of starting a business, including both intrapersonal and extra personal impacts” (Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000:419).
- PF refers to “the degree to which one feels personally capable of starting a business” (Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000:419).
- PTA is conceptualised as “the personal disposition to act on one’s decisions, thus reflecting volitional aspects of intentions” (Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000:419).

The EEM has been used on numerous occasions to analyse EI (Ahmad, Tehseen, Mahali & Qureshi, 2019:5; Davids, 2017:49; Schaegel & Koenig, 2014:304). Findings have supported the EEM as a consistent theory for predicting EI.

2.5.2 Application of the entrepreneurial event model

The findings of studies in which the EEM was tested are presented in this section. Table 2.2 summarises the results.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM

Researcher(s)	Aim of the study	Sample/nation	Results
Lara-Bocanegra, Bohorquez, Grimaldi-Puyana, Galvez-Ruiz and Garcia-Fernandez (2020:9)	The EEM was used in this study to examine the impact of a sport entrepreneurship workshop on PD, PF, and EI, as well as the relationship among these concepts.	108 people enrolled in the entrepreneurship sport workshop at the University of Seville, Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • EI was significantly influenced by PD and PF. • The model did not include PTA.
Li and Zhang (2020:8)	This study used the EEM to examine the role of PD and PF and their interaction in university scholars' EI.	252 academic entrepreneurs in China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The findings provided partial support for the EEM. • EI was significantly influenced by PF. • PD had an insignificant influence on' EI. • The model did not include PTA.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM (continued)

Researcher(s)	Aim of the study	Sample/nation	Results
Mikić, Horvatinović and Turčić (2020:365)	This study used the EEM to determine what causes EI among undergraduate students.	223 students in enrolled in an entrepreneurship course in Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • Both PD and PF had a statistically significant positive effect on EI. • PTA had a negative and statistically insignificant effect on EI.
Soomro, Lakhan, Mangi and Shah (2020:226)	This study examined the EI of business students at public sector universities using the EEM.	310 business students in Pakistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The findings provided partial support the for EEM. • EI was significantly influenced by PD and PF. • The study did not include PTA.
Ahmad <i>et al.</i> (2019:5)	This study examined Malaysian university students' EI using the EEM.	160 undergraduate students at Malaysian universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD and PF had a significant influence on students' EI. • PTA was not integrated in the model.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Ranga, Jain and Venkateswarlu (2019:968)	This study used the EEM to explore EI of management students.	125 students in India.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided full support for the EEM. • There was a statistically significant relationship between PD, PF, and PTA and EI.
Tiwari <i>et al.</i> (2019:9-10)	This study identified EI among nascent entrepreneurs in India through the EEM.	250 nascent entrepreneurs in India.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results provided partial support for the EEM. • EI had a significant relationship with PD and PF. • PTA was not integrated in the model. • The model accounted for 51% of the variation in EI.
Yamina and Mohammed (2019:277)	This study examined the EI of master's students using the EEM.	165 master's students at the University of Tlemcen in Algeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PTA and PF had a statistically significant positive impact on EI. • PTA was not integrated in the model. • The model explained between 57.7% and 67.8% of the variance in EI.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Purwana and Suhud (2018:152-154)	This study used the EEM to predict EI of vocational school students.	208 vocational school students in Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results did not support the EEM. • All variables of the EEM had an insignificant influence on EI.
Davids (2017:49)	This study used the EEM to predict EI among final-year students.	123 students at University of Cape Town in SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • EI was significantly predicted by PD, PF, and PTA. • Model accounted 38% of the variation within EI.
Mbuqe (2017:54-55)	This study used the EEM to examine the EI of SA MBA students.	153 MBA students in SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD and PTA had a significant positive effect on EI. • PF was found insignificant in influencing EI. • Model explained 67.5% of the variance in EI.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Ali, Shah and Anwar (2016:45-47)	This study identified factors that may influence students' intentions towards entrepreneurship using the EEM.	304 graduate and master's students in Thailand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD and PF had a significant positive effect on EI. • PTA was not integrated in the model.
Ndaghu, Gwen, Wajiga and Augustine (2016:24)	This study examined the relevance of the EEM in revealing the determinants of intentions and attitudes of undergraduates students towards entrepreneurship and business development.	107 final-year students in Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PF and PD had a significant influence on students' EI. • The model did not incorporate PTA. • The model accounted for 64.7 percent of the variance in EI.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Silangen (2016:78)	Using the EEM, this study investigated the link between education and EI amongst university students'.	180 final-year students within Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD had a significant impact on EI. • PF had no significant influence on EI. • PTA was not integrated in the model.
Soomro and Shah (2016:47)	This study identified factors that may influence students' intentions towards entrepreneurship through the EEM.	304 final-year students in India	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD and PF had a positive and statistically significant relationship with EI, while PTA was excluded from the model.
Yatribi (2016:45-46)	The study used the EEM to explain the EI among the employees, specifically among the executives-engineers.	376 graduates from numerous engineering schools in Morocco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD and PF both had a significant and positive effect on EI. • PTA moderated the relationship between PD and EI.

Table 2.2: Findings of studies that tested the EEM (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Schlaegel and Koenig (2014:307)	This study meta-analytically tested and integrated the TPB and EEM to examine the empirical fit of the competing theories and the integrated model.	98 studies (123 independent samples, n = 114 007), a summary of all studies included in the meta-analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PTA seemed to have no effect on EI, while PD and PF had a positive and significant effect. • The model accounted for 21% of the variation in EI.
Zhang, Duyster and Cloodt (2014:634)	The TPB, EEM, and entrepreneurial cognition theory were used in this study to determine the relationship between EE, prior entrepreneurial exposure, PD, PF, and EI among university students.	494 students from 10 Chinese universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings provided partial support for the EEM. • PD had a statistically significant influence on EI. • PF seemed to have no statistically significant effect on students' EI. • PTA was not integrated in the model.

Source: Developed by researcher

According to Table 2.2, the majority of studies that tested the EEM partially supported the model's ability to influence EI. (for example, Lara-Bocanegra *et al.*, 2020:9; Li & Zhang, 2020:8; Mikić, Horvatinović & Turčić, 2020:365; Soomro *et al.*, 2020:226; Ahmad *et al.*, 2019:5; Tiwari *et al.*, 2019:9-10; Yamina & Mohammed, 2019:277; Mbuqe, 2017:54-55; Ali, Shah & Anwar, 2016:45-47; Ndaghu *et al.*, 2016:24; Silangen, 2016:78; Soomro & Shah, 2016:47; Yatribi, 2016:45-46; Schaeigel & Koenig, 2014:304; Zhang, Duyster & Cloodt, 2014:634). However, not all researchers who evaluated EEM used all of the variables that Shapero and Sokol (1982:72) recommended. Some scholars excluded PTA from the model and added other variables instead (Soomro *et al.*, 2020:226; Ahmad *et al.*, 2019:5; Tiwari *et al.*, 2019:9-10; Yamina & Mohammed, 2019:277; Ali, Shah & Anwar, 2016:45-47; Ndaghu *et al.*, 2016:24; Silangen, 2016:78; Soomro & Shah, 2016:47; Zhang, Duyster & Cloodt, 2014:634). Ranga, Jain, and Venkateswarlu (2019:968) and Davids (2017:49) studied all of the EEM variables and discovered that PD, PTA and PF were all significant in influencing EI and fully supported the EEM. Contrary to the findings of Ranga, Jain, and Venkateswarlu (2019:968) and Davids (2017:49), Purwana and Suhud (2018:152-154) tested all EEM variables on students and discovered that they had an insignificant influence on EI.

2.5.3 The theory of planned behaviour and the determinants of intention

The TPB, its application to the field of entrepreneurship, and empirical evidence of its application are all discussed in this section of the report.

The TPB (Ajzen, 2012:438) has emerged as one of the most prevailing and prominent theoretical models for the investigation of human action (Ajzen, 2011:1117), specifically the individual's intentions to actively participate in various activities. The TPB's primary function is to provide a complete and accurate foundation for describing the aspects of behaviour (Ajzen, 2015:125). The TPB makes the assumption that intention predicts people's behaviour (Ajzen 1991:180), where intention refers to the amount of effort a person intends to make or carry through that behaviour in the future (Entrialgo & Iglesias, 2016:1211). The intention of an individual to perform a given behaviour is the TPB's central construct (Ajzen, 2012:438-459; 2011:1113-1127; 1991:179-211). It is built on the idea that people make rational choices and intentions,

and that those choices and intentions lead towards certain behaviour (Küttim, Kallaste, Venesaar & Kiis, 2014:663). The TPB is part of a wide family of intention models that have been used in the field of entrepreneurship several times, yielding reliable research results (Fayolle, Gailly & Lassas-Clerc, 2006:701; Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000:411; Shapero & Sokol 1982:72). The TPB's application to various fields including EE is well documented (Aharbi, Almahdi & Mosbah, 2018:245; Deb & Wiklund, 2017:32; Ebewo, Rugimbana & Shambare, 2017:278; Liñán & Fayolle, 2015:907; Prabandari & Sholihab, 2015:385; Fayolle, Liñán & Moriano, 2014:679; Küttim *et al.*, 2014:658; Zhang, Duysters & Cloudt, 2014:623).

TPB considers that intentions and behaviour are the results of three main predictors (Ajzen, 1991:182). To be more exact, according to the TPB, intentions are influenced by three predictors: ATB, PBC, and SN (Ajzen, 1991:182). The first predictor, ATB, takes into account an individual's positive and negative evaluations of certain behaviours. SN, the second predictor, generally reflects the social pressure (from friends, family, colleagues, etc.) on an individual to start a business or not. Last but not least, PBC reflects an individual's ability and capability to perform a specific behaviour (Ajzen, 2012:440; 2007:118; 1991:182). Figure 2.4 illustrates the determinants of intentions in the TPB.

Figure 2.4: Theory of planned behaviour

Source: Ajzen (2007:117; 1991:186)

According to Ajzen (1991:188), the stronger an individual's intention to perform the behaviour under consideration, the more favourable the attitude and SN, and the greater the PBC. Nevertheless, it is possible that the importance of ATB, PBC, and SN varies depending on the behaviour. As a result, in some cases, it may be discovered that only attitude has a significant impact on EI, or that attitude and PBC are significant, or that all three predictors are significant in explaining EI.

According to the TPB, attitudinal factors such as beliefs about an outcome influence EI (Al-Jubari, Hassan & Liñán, 2019:1324; Ajzen, 1991:179).

2.5.3.1 Attitude towards behaviour (ATB)

ATB refers to “the degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation or appraisal of the behaviour in question” (Ajzen, 1991:188). Hence, a significantly positive ATB implies that an individual tends to prefer entrepreneurship over other employment options (Ajzen, 2012:448; 1991:190). The total set of accessible behavioural beliefs linking the behaviour to various outcomes and other attributes, according to the TPB, determines attitudes (Ajzen, 2012:442). In other words, when the attributes that are associated with the behaviour have already been valued as positive or negative, they automatically and instantly obtain an ATB (Ajzen, 2007:123; 1991:191). Ajzen and Cote (2008:302) alluded that people's ATB is measured by their evaluations of the behaviour's results and the strength of the correlations with these evaluations. According to Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:94), people are more likely to see entrepreneurship as a feasible career choice if they genuinely think it will yield the desired outcome. Regarding EI among university students, empirical studies have found that ATB has a significant positive effect on EI (Galvão, Marques & Marques, 2018:726; Ahmed, Chandran & Klobas, 2017:8-13; Iglesias-Sánchez, Jambrino-Maldonado, Velasco & Kokash, 2016:216; Malebana & Swanepoel, 2015:99).

For instance, a study by Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:99-103) found that ATB positively influenced EI of students in rural areas of SA. Shah and Soomro (2017:847) corroborated that ATB positively influenced EI among public sector university students in Pakistan. Iglesias-Sánchez *et al.* (2016:216) studied entrepreneurship among

students at Malaga University. They discovered that ATB improved students' EI significantly. Samo and Hashim (2016:9) established the notable importance of ATB as a predictor of students' EI. Galvão, Marques and Marques (2018:726) indicated that ATB was the main predictor of EI among students in vocational training programmes. Thus according to Ebewo, Rugimbana, and Shambare (2017:282), students who have a positive ATB are more likely to become entrepreneurs after finishing their studies. Similar results have been found by other studies (Al-Shammari & Waleed, 2018:48; Naia, Baptista, Biscaia, Januário & Trigo 2017:16; Wach & Wojciechowski, 2016:87; Malebana & Swanepoel, 2015:99; Malebana, 2014:137).

2.5.3.2 Subjective norms (SN)

SN refers to “the perceived social pressure to perform or not to perform the behaviour” (Ajzen, 1991:188). In other words, people evaluate the beliefs of ‘referents,’ and then feel the social stigma to engage or not to engage in a certain behaviour (Ajzen, 2007:124; 1991:195). SN are people's perceptions of whether or not they should become entrepreneurs (Soomro, Shah & Memon, 2018:9). SN has been shown to have a significant effect on intentions in a number of studies (Shah & Soomro, 2017:847; Wach & Wojciechowski, 2016:87; Krithika & Venkatachalam, 2014:49-50), while others did not support this finding (Galvão, Marques & Marques, 2018:726; Naia *et al.*, 2017:16).

Nieuwenhuizen and Swanepoel (2015:4) compared the capacity of the TPB to predict the EI of students in SA and Poland. According to their results, PBC and ATB had a positive impact on intentions, but not with regard to SN. Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:100) studied the EI of 355 final-year commerce students from two universities in rural SA's Eastern Cape and Limpopo province. The TPB proved to be a useful model for determining students' entrepreneurial intentions, according to their findings. They also found that ATB accounted for the greatest variation in EI, followed by PBC. SN were not significant in predicting EI (Malebana & Swanepoel, 2015:100-104). However, Krithika and Venkatachalam (2014:49) found that SN had a significant positive influence on business students' EI in Bangalore. Similarly, Shah and Soomro (2017:847) applied the TPB on public sector university students in Pakistan and found

that SN had a statistically significant relationship with EI. Moreover, Wach and Wojciechowski (2016:87) reported similar findings on students' EI in Poland.

2.5.3.3 Perceived behavioural control (PBC)

PBC plays a significant role in the TPB (Ajzen, 1991:183). Ajzen (2005:125) mentioned that the availability of second-hand information about the behaviour, the consequences of acquaintances' and friends' actions, and the presence of factors that can facilitate the performance of the behaviour can all improve PBC. PBC refers to "the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour and it is assumed to reflect past experience as well as anticipated impediments and obstacles" (Ajzen, 1991:188). According to Ajzen (2012:447), PBC can indirectly affect behavioural performance by influencing intentions to engage in and tolerate the behaviour in the face of problems that arise during execution.

Several studies have confirmed the relationship between PBC and EI (Galvão, Marques & Marques, 2018:729; Naia *et al.*, 2017:16; Iglesias-Sánchez *et al.*, 2016:216; Malebana & Swanepoel, 2015:99; Malebana, 2014:136). For example, Galvão, Marques and Marques (2018:729) studied 289 third-year students in vocational training and found that PBC had a moderate effect on students' EI. Similarly, Naia *et al.* (2017:15) studied 379 conveniently sampled students to test Ajzen's TPB in sport sciences, with the purpose of determining which variables most influenced students' EI. Their findings revealed that PBC has a significant positive influence on EI (Naia *et al.*, 2018:16). Moreover, Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:99) studied the EI of 355 final-year commerce students at two universities in SA's rural provinces (Limpopo and Eastern Cape). Their findings revealed that PBC, along with ATB, explained the most variance in EI. Astonishingly and contradictory to Ajzen's view and previous studies on the TPB, Shah and Soomro (2017:849) reported that PBC had no significant effect on EI among university students in Pakistan.

2.5.4 Application of the theory of planned behaviour

Other studies on which tested the TPB are presented in this section. The empirical findings of these studies are summarized in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Aga and Singh (2020:2383)	This study used the TPB to predict EI of students in Ethiopian public universities.	366 final-year students from three universities in Ethiopia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results fully supported the TPB. • PBC, ATB, and SN all had a significant influence on EI. • The model explained 64.5% of the variation in EI.
Alshebami, Al-Jubari, Alyoussef and Raza (2020:3610)	This study examined the relationship between EI and EE among students of a community college of Abqiaq at King Faisal University.	184 students in Saudi Arabia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study results partially supported the TPB. • ATB had a positive and significant effect on EI, whereas SN had no statistically significant effect on EI. • The study did not include PBC.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Bhinekawati, Nelloh and Abdurahman (2020:90-91)	This study investigated the relationships between SN, PBC and EI among villagers in Bukit Peramun using the TPB.	100 local residents in Bukit Peramun, Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results partially supported the TPB. • PBC and SN had a positive and significant effect on EI. • ATB was not integrated within the model. • The model accounted for 40.7% the variation in EI.
Ilman, Ananda and Pohan (2020:1273-1275)	This study analysed the role of EE in a university environment on students' EI using the TPB.	287 students at the Sumbawa University of Technology, Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study results fully supported the TPB. • The effects of ATB, PBC, and SN on EI were statistically significant. • The model explained 50 percent of the variance in EI.
Mahmoud, Garba, Abdullah and Ali (2020:204)	The moderating effect of compulsory EE programs on the link between ATB, PBC, SN and EI was investigated in this study.	293 students in Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study results partially supported the TPB. • ATB had a significant relationship with EI. • SN and PBC had an insignificant relationship with EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Agollo, Monametsi and Phera (2019:47)	This study examined the antecedents of EI among open- and distance-learning students during an employment crisis using the TPB.	500 students in Botswana.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant relationship with EI. • SN had an insignificant relationship with EI • Model explained 62.2% of the variation in EI.
Feola, Vesci, Botti and Parente (2019:1433-1436)	This study used the TPB to identify the determinants of academic EI.	213 PhD students in the science and technical departments of four universities located in southern Italy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a statistically significant and positive influence on EI. • Model accounted for 49.8% of the variation in EI.
Mothibi and Malebana (2019:8) and Mothibi (2018:78)	This study used the TPB to examine the determinants of EI among secondary school learners in Mamelodi, SA.	349 learners from 11 secondary schools in Mamelodi, SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, PBC and SN had a significant positive relationship with EI. • Model explained 39% of the variation in EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Paiva, Sousa, Lima and Silva (2019:16)	This study investigated the relationship between religious beliefs and constructs of the TPB in EI.	448 business administration students from public universities in Brazil.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant and positive relationship with EI. • SN had no significant relationship with EI. • Model accounted for 59% of the variance in EI.
Urban and Chantson (2019:967)	This study examined and extended the TPB by including institutional and organisational factors to ascertain levels of EI among academic scientists in SA.	247 researcher scientists in SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a statistically significant and positive influence on EI. • Model accounted for 92% of the variation in EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Wibowo (2019:7)	This study investigated the role of entrepreneurial motivation in the context of TPB by comparing two models.	273 final-year students in Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results partially supported the TPB. • PBC and ATB had a significant positive effect on EI. • SN had no significant influence on EI.
Marire and Dhurup (2018:200-201)	This study used the TPB to examine the influence of the antecedents of EI among Generation Y university students in SA and Zimbabwe.	400 students from universities in SA and Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a statistically significant and positive relationship with EI for both South African and Zimbabwean students.
Awan and Ahmad (2017:24-25)	The TPB was used in this study to investigate the intentions of university students in Karachi when establishing new businesses.	250 university students within Pakistan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a statistically significant and positive effect on EI. • SN did not significantly influence EI. • Model explained 65% of the variation in EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Davids (2017:48)	This study used the TPB to predict EI among final-year students.	123 students at University of Cape Town, SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant positive effect on EI. • SN did not significantly influence EI. • Model explained 58% of the variation in EI.
Feder and Nițu-Antonie (2017:98)	This study used the TPB investigated the antecedents of EI among youth beneficiaries of entrepreneurial higher education studies.	650 students in Romania.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study results fully supported the TPB. • Personal attitude, SN and PBC had a significant positive influence on EI. • Model explained 50.8% of the variance in EI.
Marire, Mafini and Dhurup (2017:27)	This study examined the influence of personal attitude, SN, PBC and EE on EI among Generation Y students in Zimbabwe.	200 students in Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant influence on EI. • SN had an insignificant influence on EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Mwiya, Wang, Shikaputo, Kaulungombe and Kayekesi (2017:602)	This study examined the influence of social norms, personal attitudes and PBC on business start-up intentions using the TPB.	306 final-year undergraduate students at a public university in Zambia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • SN, ATB and PBC were statistically significant relationship with EI. • The model accounted for 54.3% of the variation in EI.
Tarek (2017:79)	The TPB was used in this study to examine the EI of Tunisian final-year university students.	400 final-year students in Tunisia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a significant positive effect on EI. • The model accounted for 60% of the variance in EI.
Tarek (2016:350)	The purpose of this study was to see if the TPB could help explain the EI of university students.	283 fourth-year business management students in Saudi Arabia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a significant positive effect on EI. • Model accounted for 54.3% of the variation in EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Xu, Ni and Ye (2016:631)	This study used the TPB to examine the status of EE in secondary schools and discover the determinants of EI.	1 034 secondary-school students in China.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant positive effect on EI, while the effect of SN was not significant.
Buli and Yesuf (2015:899)	This study looked at factors that could explain the differences in EI among students enrolled in technical-vocational education and training (TVET) programs using the TPB.	107 TVET students in Ethiopia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant positive effect on EI. • SN did not significantly influence EI. • Model explained 44.6% of the variation in EI.
Hussain and Norashidah (2015:49)	The purpose of this study was to test the effects of EE on EI and to validate the TPB in predicting students' EI.	499 university students in Sindh, Pakistan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a significant positive relationship with EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Kautonen, Van Gelderen and Fink (2015:666)	This study investigated the robustness of the TPB in predicting EI.	969 adults from Austria and Finland.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, PBC and SN had a statistically significant positive influence on EI. • Model accounted for 59% of the variation in EI.
Marire (2015:66)	The TPB was used in this study to assess factors that influence EI amongst university students.	251 students in SA and Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results partially supported the TPB. • Personal attitude and PBC had a significant positive impact on EI for both South African and Zimbabwean students. • SN had an insignificant impact on EI for both South African and Zimbabwean students.
Prabandari and Sholihab (2015:389)	This study used the TPB to investigate the factors that influence the EI of students in graduate school.	165 students at Brawijaya University, Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results partially supported the TPB. • SN and PBC had a significant positive effect on EI • ATB had no significant effect on EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Pulka, Aminu and Rikwentishe (2015:154)	This study used the TPB to assess the relationship that may exist between offering an EE course and students' intentions to become entrepreneurs.	400 students from five universities in northeast Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a significant and positive effect on EI.
Rauch and Hulsink (2015:195-198)	This study used the TPB to investigate whether EE can affect entrepreneurial behaviour.	96 entrepreneurship masters students and 57 supply-chain management masters students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study results partially supported the TPB. • ATB and PBC had a significant positive influence on EI. • SN were not concluded in the study model.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Zapkau, Schwens, Steinmetz and Kabst (2015:645)	This study used the TPB to analyse whether attitude, SN and PBC mediated the influence of entrepreneurial role models and work experience on EI in small or newly founded businesses.	374 university students and information technology professionals in Germany.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • SN, ATB, and PBC had a statistically significant relationship with EI.
Mahmoud and Muharam (2014:21)	This study examined the EI of Nigerian PhD candidates based on the TPB.	130 PhD students in Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, PBC and SN had a statistically significant relationship with EI. • Model accounted for 59.4% of the variation in EI.
Malebana (2014:137)	This study investigated the EI of 329 final-year students in a rural university in the Limpopo province using the TPB.	329 final-year commerce students in the Limpopo province, SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a statistically significant relationship with EI. • Model explained for 49.2% of the variation in EI.

Table 2.3: Findings of other studies that tested the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Schlaegel and Koenig (2014:306)	This study meta-analytically tested and integrated the TPB and the EEM to examine the empirical fit of the competing theories.	98 studies (123 independent samples, n = 114 007), a summary of all studies included in the meta-analyses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results fully supported the TPB. • ATB, SN and PBC had a significant and positive effect on EI. • Model accounted for 28% of the variation in EI.

Source: Developer by researcher

Note: ATB = Attitude towards behaviour, EI = Entrepreneurial Intentions, PBC = Perceived behavioural control, SN = Subjective norms

According to Table 2.3, the majority of studies that tested the TPB discovered that ATB, PBC, and SN all had a statistically significant and positive effect on EI and thus fully supported the TPB (Aga & Singh, 2020:2383; Alshebami *et al.*, 2020:3610; Ilman, Ananda & Pohan, 2020:1273-1275; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2020:204; Feola *et al.*, 2019:1433-1436; Urban & Chantson, 2019:967; Mothibi & Malebana, 2019:8; Marire & Dhurup, 2018:200-201; Mothibi, 2018:78; Feder & Nițu-Antonie, 2017:98; Mwiya *et al.*, 2017:602; Tarek, 2017:79; Tarek, 2016:350; Hussain & Norashdah, 2015:49; Kautonen, Van Gelderen & Fink, 2015:666; Pulka, Aminu & Rikwentishe, 2015:154; Zapkau *et al.*, 2015:645; Mahmoud & Muharam, 2014:21; Malebana, 2014:137; Schlaegel & Koenig, 2014:306). Other studies that tested the TPB partially supported the model because some antecedents from the TPB had no significant relationship with EI or the studies did not include all antecedents from the TPB (Bhinekawati, Nelloh, Abdurahman, 2020:90-91; Agollo, Monametsi & Phera, 2019:47; Paiva *et al.*, 2019:16; Wibowo, 2019:7; Awan & Ahmad, 2017:24-25; Davids, 2017:48; Marire, Mafini & Dhurup, 2017:27; Xu, Ni & Ye, 2016:631; Buli & Yesuf, 2015:899; Marire, 2015:66; Prabandari & Sholihab, 2015:389; Rauch & Hulsink, 2015:195-198).

2.6 THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOUR AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

This section outlines the results of studies which examined effects of EE using the TPB. Table 2.4 summarises the results of these studies.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Alshebami <i>et al.</i> (2020:3610)	This study examined the relationship between EI and EE among students of a community college of Abqiaq at King Faisal University.	184 students in Saudi Arabia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive effect on EI through the mediating role of ATB.
Ilman, Ananda and Pohan (2020:1273-1275)	This study used the TPB to analyse the role of EE, university environment, in shaping students' intention.	287 students at the Sumbawa University of Technology in Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE affected EI indirectly through PBC and ATB. • EE did not affect SN. • Model explained 64.5% of the variation in EI.
Mahmoud <i>et al.</i> (2020:204)	This study evaluated the moderating effect of compulsory EE programmes on the link between ATB, SN, PBC and EI.	293 students in Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had an insignificant relationship with EI. • The moderating effect of EE on ATB, SN, PBC and EI was insignificant.
Paray and Kumar (2020:61-66)	This study used the TPB to examine the influence of EE on EI among students in higher learning institutions.	309 students in Indian higher learning institutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant impact on ATB, SN and EI. • The model explained 46.8% of the variance in EI.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Otache, Umar, Audu and Onalo (2019:14)	This study used a longitudinal approach to examine the effects of EE on students' EI through the constructs of the TPB.	250 National Diploma students in Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive relationship with ATB, PBC, SN and EI. • The model accounted for 35% of the variation in EI.
Purusittama and Akbar (2019:144)	This study utilised TPB to examine the effects of EE in promoting students EI in Indonesia.	304 students from 10 universities in Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant and positive relationship with EI and ATB. • EE had no significant influence on SN and PBC.
Wahjono, Marina and Fen (2019:263-265)	This study used the TPB to examine the effect of the business house as an EE programme to increase university students' EI.	202 university students from Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The business house as an EE programme had a statistically significant and positive relationship with ATB, SN, PBC and EI.
Zhang, Wei, Sun and Tung (2019:160)	This study explored how entrepreneurial learning impacts one's EI.	200 university students in Hong Kong, China.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial learning had a positive relationship with EI that was significantly mediated by ATB, SN and PBC.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Badr, El-Gharbowy, Wohba and Bary (2018:219)	This study used the TPB to Investigate the impact of EE in Egyptian universities.	400 undergraduate students in Egypt.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive relationship with ATB, PBC and SN. • The link between EE and EI was not tested.
Marire and Dhurup (2018:200-201)	This study used the TPB to examine the effect of EE on the antecedents of EI among Generation Y university students in Zimbabwe and SA.	400 students from universities in SA and Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a direct significant and positive relationship with EI for both Zimbabwean and South African students. • The relationship between personal attitude, SN, PBC and EE was not tested.
Ahmed, Chandran and Klobas (2017:11-13)	This study used the TPB as conceptual framework and compared the difference in entrepreneurial attitude, SN, PBC and intentions among students who partake in EE with a control group of MBA students in Pakistan	329 MBA students and 348 entrepreneurship students in their final year from Pakistan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study did not find any difference in ATB, SN and PBC towards entrepreneurship in MBA and EE programme students. • EE had a significant positive influence on the EI of MBA and EE programme students. • EE had a significant positive influence on ATB, SN and PBC.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Aloulou (2017:12-16)	Based on the TPB, this study determined the factors that influence final-year Saudi business students' intentions to become entrepreneurs before and after completing an entrepreneurship course at university.	151 business college students at Al Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University, Saudi Arabia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entrepreneurship course had a significant impact on ATB and EI. • Entrepreneurship course had no significant relationship with SN and PBC.
Ebewo (2017:143)	This study used the TPB to investigate the mediating effects of the antecedents of entrepreneurship intention on the effects of the entrepreneurial environment on EI.	175 BTech arts students in SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATB and perceived entrepreneurial ability mediated the relationship between EE and EI. • SN did not mediate the relationship between EE and EI.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Ebewo, Rugimbana and Shambare (2017:287)	This study examined the effects of EE on students' EI at the University of Botswana.	343 final-year students at the University of Botswana.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in EE had a significant positive relationship with EI, ATB and perceived entrepreneurial ability. • No significant relationship existed between EE and SN.
Feder and Nițu-Antonie (2017:98)	The TPB was used to examine the antecedents of EI among youth beneficiaries of entrepreneurial higher education studies.	650 students in Romania.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational background had no statistically significant positive influence on ATB, SN and PBC. • Educational background had a statistically significant and positive relationship with EI.
Marire, Mafini and Dhurup (2017:27)	This study investigated the influence of personal attitude, SN, PBC and EE on EI amongst Generation Y students in Zimbabwe.	200 students in Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a direct significant and positive relationship with EI. • The relationship between personal attitude, SN, PBC and EE was not tested.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Ndofirepi and Rambe (2017:196)	This study used the TPB to examine EE and its impact on the entrepreneurship career intentions of vocational education students.	154 students in Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a positive correlation with ATB, SN, PBC and EI.
Rambe, Ndofirepi and Dzansi (2017:544); Ndofirepi (2016:190)	This study used the TPB to explore the collective impact of technological creativity and exposure to EE on the EI of students at tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe and SA.	284 students in Zimbabwe and SA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE and technological creativity had a significant effect on SN and PBC for both South African and Zimbabwean students. • EE and technological creativity had a significant effect on Zimbabwean students' ATB and an insignificant effect on South African students' ATB. • EE and technological creativity had an insignificant direct effect on EI for both South African and Zimbabwean students.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Sun, Lo, Liang and Wong (2017:1382-1383)	This study investigated the impact of EE on EI with a view to address the gaps in previous research based on the TPB.	200 engineering students from three universities in Hong Kong, China.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE a significant and positive relationship with SN, ATB PBC and EI. • Model explained 50% of the variance in EI.
Entrialgo and Iglesias (2016:1221-1225)	This study examined the role of EE in explaining EI.	111 final-year Spanish students in Spain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant role in mitigating the relationship between SN, ATB, PBC and EI.
Karimi, Biemans, Lans, Chizari and Mulder (2016b:195-199)	This study assessed the impacts of elective and compulsory EE programmes on students' EI.	205 participants at six Ranian universities in India.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a statistically significant effect on students' EI, SN and PBC. • EE had no significant effect on ATB.
Khalifa and Dhiaf (2016:123-125)	This study explored the impact of EE on EI in the United Arab Emirates context using the TPB.	400 students in the United Arab Emirates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE did not affect EI. • No statistically significant relationship existed between SN, ATB, PBC and EE.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Iglesias-Sánchez <i>et al.</i> (2016:220)	This study examined the impact of entrepreneurship programmes on university students.	382 students at Malaga University in Spain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive effect on ATB, PBC and EI. • EE had no significant effect on SN.
Ajike <i>et al.</i> (2015:128-130)	The TPB was used in this study to look into the effect of EE on the EI of students from various private universities.	168 final-year business students in Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive relationship with EI, ATB, SN and PBC.
Hussain and Norashidah (2015:49)	The purpose of this study was to test the effects of EE on EI and to validate the TPB in predicting students' EI in Pakistan.	499 university students in Sindh, Pakistan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a direct impact on EI. • The relationship between ATB, SN, PBC and EE was not tested.
Marire (2015:66)	The TPB was used in this study to assess factors that contribute to EI in university students in SA and Zimbabwe.	251 students in SA and Zimbabwe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a statistically significant and positive relationship with EI for both SA and Zimbabwean students.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Murugesan and Jayavelu (2015:269)	This study used the TPB to test the impact of EE on business, engineering, and art and science students.	450 students in India.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive relationship with EI, attitude towards self-employment, SN and PBC. <p>Model accounted for 55.3% of the variation in EI.</p>
Prabandari and Sholihab (2015:389)	This study used the TPB to investigate the factors that influence the EI of students in the graduate school.	165 students at Brawijaya University, Indonesia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive effect on ATB, PBC and EI. • EE had no statistically significant relationship with SN.
Pulka, Aminu and Rikwentishe (2015:154)	This study used the TPB to assess the relationship that may exist between offering an EE course and students' intentions to become entrepreneurs.	400 students from five universities in northeast Nigeria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a direct and significant positive relationship with EI. • The relationship between ATB, SN, PBC and EE was not tested.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Rauch and Hulsink (2015:195-198)	This study used the TPB to investigate whether EE can affect entrepreneurial behaviour.	96 entrepreneurship masters students and 57 supply-chain management masters students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a significant positive effect on ATB, PBC and EI. • SN were not included in the study.
Heuer and Kolvereid (2014:515)	This study investigated the relationship between education in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial behaviour.	1 062 graduates and students from Belgium and Norway (261 Norwegian graduates and 807 Belgian students).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had no significant effect on ATB, SN and PBC. • EE had a direct influence on EI.

Table 2.4: Studies which examined the effects of entrepreneurship education using the TPB (continued)

Researcher(s)	Purpose	Sample/nation	Results
Küttim <i>et al.</i> (2014:665)	This study identified the content of university EE and its impact on students' EI.	55 781 students from 17 European countries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE had a positive impact on ATB, SN, PBC and EI.
Karali (2013:34)	The purpose of this study was to look into the impact of entrepreneurship programs on the EI of students in higher education in the Netherlands.	13 121 students from 19 universities in the Netherlands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in EE had a statistically significant influence on EI, ATB, SN and PBC.

Source: Developed by researcher

Note: **EE** = Entrepreneurship education; **PBC** = Perceived behavioural control; **ATB** = Attitude towards behaviour; **EI** = Entrepreneurial intentions; **SN** = Subjective norms

According to Table 2.4, many empirical studies that researched the effects of EE agree on its capability to fully influence EI (Otache *et al.*, 2019:14; Wahjono, Marina & Fen, 2019:263-265; Zhang *et al.*, 2019:160; Badr *et al.*, 2018:219; Ahmed, Chandran & Klobas, 2017:11-13; Ndofirepi & Rambe, 2017:196; Sun *et al.*, 2017:1382-1383; Entrialgo & Iglesias, 2016:1221-1225; Ndofirepi, 2016:190; Murugesan & Jayavelu, 2015:269; Ajike *et al.*, 2015:128-130; Küttim *et al.*, 2014:665; Karali, 2013:34). However, some studies have shown that the effects of EE on students' intentions to become entrepreneurs are significantly influenced by their ATB and PBC (Ilman, Ananda & Pohan, 2020:1273-1275; Ebewo, 2017:143; Ebewo, Rugimbana & Shambare, 2017:287; Iglesias Sánchez *et al.*, 2016:220; Maresh *et al.*, 2016:176; Ndofirepi, 2016:190; Prabandari & Sholihab, 2015:389; Rauch & Hulsink, 2015:195-198). Some studies found a direct and statistically significant relationship between EE and EI (Marire & Dhurup, 2018:200-201; Marire, Mafini & Dhurup, 2017:27; Feder & Nițu-Antonie, 2017:98; Marire, 2015:66; Pulka, Aminu & Rikwentishe, 2015:154; Heuer & Kolvereid, 2014:515).

Nevertheless, other authors discovered that EE had no statistically significant influence on SN and PBC (Purusittama & Akbar, 2019:144; Alshebami *et al.*, 2020:3610; Aloulou, 2017:12-16). Karimi *et al.* (2016b:195-199) asserted that EE had no significant effect on students' ATB. On the other hand, Mahmoud *et al.* (2020:204) and Khalifa and Dhiab (2016:123-125) revealed that EE did not affect EI and had no statistically significant relationship with SN. Though many studies differed in terms of their methodology and theoretical orientation, the majority concluded that entrepreneurship training appears to have a significant influence on students' EI. The results of some of these studies suggested that the TPB is a valuable model for understanding the impact of EE on students' EI.

2.7 OTHER FACTORS WHICH INFLUENCE ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS

In this section, other factors which influence EI based on the TPB are discussed.

2.7.1 Gender and entrepreneurial intentions

Gender plays a significant part in assessing EI (Robledo, Aran, Sanchez & Molina, 2015:98). According to Miranda, Chamorro-Mera, Rubio and Perez-Mayo (2017:72), gender has long been thought to be one of the factors influencing the process of commercializing research findings. Feder and Nițu-Antonie (2017:101) argued that providing EE based on gender identification and merging it with the knowledge and experience of entrepreneurs and researchers can enhance the success of entrepreneurship proficiency development.

Karimi, Biemans, Lans, Chizari and Mulder (2014:705-712) used the TPB to explore the effect of gender on students' EI. In their findings, they discovered that gender had a significant relationship with ATB, PBC, SN and EI. Their results further indicated that female students had a significantly higher (better) ATB and experienced more SN than their male counterparts. However, no statistically significant gender differences in the relationship between PBC and EI were discovered (Karimi *et al.*, 2014:705-712). Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:100) also discovered that gender had a significant relationship with ATB, PBC, SN and EI. Feder and Nițu-Antonie (2017:98) discovered that gender had a significant positive influence on PBC, SN and EI, but no significant effect on ATB. Feder and Nițu-Antonie (2017:98) further discovered that gender had a significant positive influence on SN for female students and an insignificant negative influence for their male counterparts. Malebana (2015:619) discovered a significant positive relationship between gender and PBC, SN, ATB, and entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Malebana (2015:619) further discovered that male students had a considerably higher EI, more positive ATB, perceived that their immediate family, friends, and colleagues would approve of their decision to start a business, and had substantially higher PBC and entrepreneurial self-efficacy than their female counterparts.

Maes, Leroy and Sels (2014:790) reported that gender had a statistically significant effect on personal attitude and PBC. No significant relationship was found between gender, EI and SN. Maes, Leroy and Sels (2014:790) further reported that personal attitude and PBC were notably higher among male students than their female counterparts. Robledo *et al.* (2015:98) revealed that gender had a significant positive

influence on ATB, PBC and EI and an insignificant relationship with SN. Their findings further discovered that female students are more motivated to pursue entrepreneurship than their male counterparts (Robledo *et al.*, 2015:99).

Palupi and Santoso (2017:75-77) examined the effects of gender on EI through the antecedents proposed by the TPB. Their findings demonstrated that gender had a statistically significant influence on PBC, SN, ATB and EI. However, there was no difference in perceptions of entrepreneurship between male and female respondents. Mothibi (2018:79) discovered that there was no statistically significant difference between males and females in EI, ATB, and PBC. His results further showed that both male and female respondents had a similar score in EI, ATB and PBC. Males' perceived social norms were significantly higher than females'. In comparison to their male counterparts, these findings indicated that females were less likely to be swayed by their immediate school members, family members, and friends in their decision to start a business (Mothibi, 2018:79).

2.7.2 Age and entrepreneurial intentions

In addition to gender differences, age has often been investigated in studies related to entrepreneurship (Chaudhary, 2017:175). Researchers have proposed that age may act as a moderator of EI (Sahut, Gharbi & Mili, 2015:260; Kautonen, Down & Minniti, 2014:592). For instance, Malebana and Swanepoel (2015:102) discovered that age had a significant relationship with EI and PBC. They further revealed that age had no statistically significant relationship with SN or ATB (Malebana & Swanepoel, 2015:101). Sahut, Gharbi and Mili (2015:260) tested the magnitude and direction of the correlation between age and EI, and discovered that age had a statistically significant negative relationship with EI. Similarly, Hatak, Harms and Fink (2015:52) reported that age had a negative effect on EI. Paray and Kumar (2020:61) revealed that age had no influence on EI or any of the antecedents of the TPB. Jo and Anuoluwapo (2019:36) discovered a significant negative relationship between age and ATB and EI. There was no significant relationship found between age and PBC or SN (Jo & Anuoluwapo, 2019:36). The empirical findings on age and EI presented above show that age does not have a positive and significant influence on the TPB factors that affect EI.

2.7.3 Family background and entrepreneurial intentions

Numerous studies have suggested a positive relation between family background and EI (Mothibi & Malebana, 2019:7; Chaudhary, 2017:179; Joseph, 2017:424; Malebana, 2016b:63; Xu, Ni & Ye, 2016:630; Malebana, 2014:136). According to Ozaralli and Rivenburgh (2016:27), families with entrepreneurial types of jobs offer younger individuals with the opportunity to receive specific business knowledge, experience, self-belief, and vision to help them build their own enterprises. Malebana (2016b:63) revealed that entrepreneurial family background had a statistically significant positive relationship with ATB and EI. However, no relationship was discovered between PBC and entrepreneurial family background (Malebana, 2016b:63). Galvão, Marques and Marques (2018:727) discovered that having an entrepreneurial family background had a statistically significant influence on PBC and EI

Xu, Ni, and Ye (2016:630) uncovered that students from entrepreneurial families outperformed those from non-entrepreneurial families on all four key variables. Malebana (2014:136) discovered a statistically significant negative relationship between entrepreneurial family background and ATB, SN, PBC, and EI. Contrary to Malebana's (2014:136) findings, Mothibi and Malebana (2019:7) discovered that entrepreneurial family background had a statistically significant relationship with EI and all the antecedents of the TPB.

2.7.4 Entrepreneurial experience or prior work experience and entrepreneurial intentions

According to Ashraf (2020:12), "prior work experience is measured as an individual's practical experience working with different social-sector organisations." Zhang, Duysters and Cloudt (2014:623) argued that exposure to entrepreneurship through family members, friends and employers improves individuals' EI. For instance, Fatoki (2014:294) reported that students with previous work experience showed a higher level of EI than students without previous work experience. Zapkau *et al.* (2015:649) showed that prior working experience influenced EI through ATB and PBC, but not with regard to SN. A more recent study by Yuan, Qalati, Iqbal, Hussain and Ali

(2019:878) investigated the impact of previous work experience on EI in Pakistan. Their findings showed that previous work experience had a positive relationship with EI, which was mediated by PBC, SN and ATB (Yuan *et al.*, 2019:878).

In relation to prior start-up experience, Muller, Zapkau and Schwens (2014:266) examined how the influence of entrepreneurial exposure on EI is contingent on national culture and found that prior entrepreneurial exposure (direct experience) had a significant positive relationship with PBC and EI. Prior entrepreneurial exposure (direct experience) had no significant relationship with ATB or SN (Muller, Zapkau & Schwens, 2014:266). Miralles, Giones and Gozun (2017:894) discovered that being personally involved in entrepreneurial activities had a significant positive effect on ATB, SN, PBC and EI. Prior exposure to entrepreneurship, according to Zhang *et al.* (2019:160), moderates the indirect effect of entrepreneurial learning on EI through ATB and PBC. Prior exposure to entrepreneurship had no significant moderating effect on the effects of education on SN (Zhang *et al.*, 2019:160). Jo and Anuoluwapo (2019:36) reported that prior entrepreneurial exposure had a significant positive relationship with EI, ATB and SN. However, no significant relationship was found between prior entrepreneurial exposure and PBC (Jo & Anuoluwapo, 2019:36).

2.7.5 Role models and entrepreneurial intentions

Role models are defined as “a common reference to individuals who set examples to be emulated by others and stimulate or inspire other individuals to make certain choices and achieve certain goals” (Bosma, Hessels, Schutjens, Van Praag & Verheul, 2012:410). Entrialgo and Iglesias (2017:9) studied the effects of introducing role models in EE on 338 final-year students. Their findings revealed that social norms, ATB and PBC mediated the relationship between knowledge of the role model and EI. They also reported that people can learn the unique skills and behaviours needed to start a business by following their role models (Entrialgo & Iglesias, 2017:10). Similarly, Karimi *et al.* (2014:710) reported that parental role models have a positive and significant relationship with EI, which is mediated by ATB, SN, and PBC. Moreover, they mentioned that ATB and PBC among female students were more strongly influenced by role models compared to male students.

Malebana (2016a:103) discovered a significant but very weak relationship between entrepreneurial role models and EI and its antecedents. His study results showed that different role models have varying relationships with EI and its antecedents (Malebana, 2016a:103). Feder and Nițu-Antonie (2017:98) uncovered that having an entrepreneurial role model had a statistically significant positive influence on students' personal attitude, SN, PBC, and EI. Zapkau *et al.* (2015:645) reported that having entrepreneurial parents as role models positively influenced SN with regard to starting a business. However, parental role models had no significant effect on ATB and PBC (Zapkau *et al.*, 2015:646). Fellnhofer (2017:61) investigated the impact of entrepreneurial role models on entrepreneurial passion and intentions based on 426 individuals recruited primarily from Austria. Drawing on the TPB, her study findings revealed that entrepreneurial role models had a positive impact on ATB, SN, PBC and EI.

2.8 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The aim of the literature review chapter was to give an exposition of the literature as it pertains to entrepreneurship, EE and EI. The concepts of entrepreneurship and EE, along with the role and value of EE in the entrepreneurial process, were discussed. Two models of EI, namely the EEM and the TPB, were also discussed along with the antecedents proposed by these models. Empirical findings of studies which examined effects of EE using TPB were also discussed. The chapter also discussed other factors that influence EI. The following chapter outlines the research methodology utilised in this research.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter on research methodology describes the research procedure used for this study. The study's research objectives, research design, study population, sampling procedure, and data collection and analysis method are all discussed. The research instrument's validity and reliability, as well as ethical concerns about the study, are also discussed.

3.2 RESEARCH PROCESS

The research process has been defined as a sequential process with several clearly defined steps (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:76). These procedures or methods are used at each stage of the research process and may include procedures for sample selection, measuring variables, gathering data, as well as interpreting the results. Figure 3.1 depicts the steps in the research process model proposed by Cooper and Schindler (2014:124) for empirical research.

Figure 3.1: Research process

Source: Cooper and Schindler (2014:124)

This research followed the stages presented within Figure 3.1. Stage 1 was completed in Chapter 1. In this chapter, the primary components of stage 2, 3, 4 and 5 which refer to the research design strategies, data gathering, data analysis and research reporting methods deployed in this study are addressed. These stages are delineated through the headings and sub-sections that follow below.

3.3 IDENTIFYING THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

During this stage, the researcher recognises the research problem which should be solved (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015:45). A problem statement is a clear, brief description of an issue to be addressed or improved upon (Velazques, 2019:41). The research problem of this research is that a high youth unemployment rate has a negative effect on economic growth and productivity which cannot be ignored. This has been a cause for concern. There is a risk that qualified and talented people will be lost because a large number of graduates cannot find work and use their knowledge and skills to innovate and contribute to economic growth. However, most tertiary institutions that provide entrepreneurial training believe that promoting EE can lead to policy support, growth of the economy and employment creation. Therefore, it is vital to evaluate the degree to which EE influences EI among TUT students using the TPB.

3.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This section of the study outlines the research objectives and hypotheses of this study.

3.4.1 Primary objective

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT.

3.4.2 Secondary objectives

The following are the secondary objectives of this research:

- To assess if EE has a significant impact on students' EI.

- To determine the impact of EE on students' ATB.
- To establish the impact of EE on students' SN.
- To assess the impact EE has on students' PBC.

3.4.3 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were derived from the objectives:

H₀₁: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' EI.

H₁: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' EI.

H₀₂: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.

H₂: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.

H₀₃: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' SN.

H₃: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' SN.

H₀₄: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.

H₄: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.

3.5 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design connects the data to be gathered and the conclusions to the research's original purpose. A research design is “a set of methods and procedures used to collect, measure and analyse data” (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:136). According to Creswell (2014:12), quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methodologies study designs provide specific recommendations for research design approaches. That is, the study design clarifies the required data, the data collection and analysis methods used, and how all of these questions contribute to the research objective (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:124).

In this section, strategies of inquiry linked with quantitative research design are discussed. Quantitative research design is “a systematic and mathematical research method used to collect and analyse quantifiable data” (Gray, 2019:404). It is primarily used to investigate the relationship between variables that are numerically measured and evaluated using a variety of statistical and graphical techniques (Saunders, Lewis

& Thornhill, 2016:167). Creswell (2014:20) mentioned that, if a research problem necessitates determining the efficacy of an intervention, identifying factors that influence the outcome, or determining the best predictors of an outcome, a quantitative design is the way to go. A quantitative research methodology can be evidence-based to support or reject hypotheses at advanced or earlier stages of the research process (Creswell, 2014:41) and is commonly linked with a deductive research approach that emphasizes the use of data in theory (Bryman & Bell, 2015:160). To put it another way, quantitative studies use statistical techniques to investigate the relationship between numerically measured variables.

This research offers an insight into the influence of EE on students' EI at TUT. One of the goals is to develop an enhanced entrepreneurship programmes that can impact student EI especially in SA. As a result, a quantitative descriptive research design was adopted for data collection, data analysis and problem solving. Descriptive research is "a scientific method for studying and describing behaviour without being affected in any way" (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015:154). It depends on gathering observations to gather data and examine situations to identify the rule or what can be foretold to happen again under a similar setting (Walliman, 2017:10). Its main purpose is gaining an accurate description of the issue on which data is to be collected prior to collecting the data (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:175). Cooper and Schindler (2014:218) assert that:

"Survey research designs are procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviours, or characteristics of the population. A survey can make use of a telephone, self-administrated, mail, a computer, e-mail, or the Internet as the medium of communication, and can expand geographic coverage at a fraction of the cost and time required by observation."

Because the goal of quantitative research is to help the researcher understand the relationship between an independent and dependent variable in a population, it is well suited for learning about the relationship between EE and the key variables of this study. In cross-sectional studies, data about variables is collected at one given point of time across a sample population (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015:158). Based on the

viewpoints expressed above, the researcher decided that the quantitative approach would be appropriate to use in this research because the TPB would be used to examine the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT.

3.5.1 Population of the study

A population is the group from which a sample is drawn, and a sample is a subset of the population. Based on Cooper and Schindler's (2014:338) definition, a population is a collection of variables from which we can derive conclusions. According to information provided by the TUT Registrar Directorate, the study population consisted of 1 003 first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students in the DME.

3.5.2 Sampling procedure

According to Taherdoost (2016a:18), sampling refers to the process that is used to predetermine the number of observations taken from a larger population. Gary (2019:405) described a sample as "a set object, occurrences or individuals selected from a parent population for a research study." The researcher may choose not to include all members of a population. A representative sample is obtained to carefully generalise the results (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:274). "A sample is used to examine a portion of the target population which must be carefully selected to represent that population" (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:84). "The basic idea of sampling is that, by selecting some of the elements in a population, the researcher may be able to draw conclusions about the entire population" (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:338). The participants in this study composed of first-, second-, and third-year entrepreneurship students from TUT's DME. The decision to choose first-, second-, and third-year entrepreneurship students was based on the fact that the entrepreneurship course focuses on providing students with the necessary entrepreneurial knowledge and skills to establish and manage a new business endeavour from the first year of study all the way through to the final year. Moreover, entrepreneurship students are expected to seek gainful employment or start their own businesses during the course or soon after graduation.

3.5.2.1 Sample size determination

The size of the sample for this research was dependent on The Research Advisor (2006), which recommended the formula below to establish the sample size. The formula according to The Research Advisor (quoted by Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:280-281) is as follows:

$$n = \frac{x^2 \times N \times p(1 - p)}{(e^2 \times (N - 1)) + (x^2 \times p \times (1 - p))}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

x^2 = Chi-square for the specified confidence level at 1 degree of freedom

N = Population size

p = Population proportion (0.50)

e = Desired margin of error (expressed as a percentage in decimal)

Therefore, sample size $n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 1003 \times 0.50(1-0.50)}{(0.05^2 \times (1003-1)) + (1.96^2 \times 0.50 \times (1-0.50))}$

Sample = 278

The proposed sample size for this study was 278 first-, second-, and third-year entrepreneurial students, with a 95 percent confidence interval and a 5 percent margin of error.

3.5.2.2 Sampling technique

“Sampling techniques allow the researcher to reduce the amount of data collected by looking at data only from a smaller set of all possible cases or objects.” (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:272). The researcher can adequately achieve the research objectives by selecting the most relevant sampling method (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:298). This research utilised a convenience sampling method.

Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling method in which a sample is chosen or taken from a group of people who are easily contacted or reached (Taherdoost, 2016a:22; Leedy & Ormrod, 2015:182; Cooper & Schindler, 2014:665). Scholars commonly use convenience sampling to acquire a great number of completed questionnaires rapidly and economically (Zikmund, Babin, Carr & Griffin, 2013:393). This sampling technique was used because students studying entrepreneurship were well positioned to understand the relationship between EE and the main variables in this study and were easily accessible. In addition, the cost and time needed to perform a proper survey is much small compared to those of a probability sample. Therefore, the researcher can use convenience sampling to determine the sample relatively quickly and inexpensively.

3.5.3 Data collection

This section outlines the process of designing and administering of the questionnaire.

3.5.3.1 Questionnaire design

Primary data was gathered in order to achieve the study's research objective. The data was gathered by means of an online survey, using an EIQ that was administered to first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students from the DME at TUT. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016:437) stated that “a valid questionnaire will enable accurate data that actually measure the concepts you are interested in to be collected.” Cooper and Schindler (2014:664) defined a questionnaire as “an instrument delivered via personal or non-personal means to be completed by the participant.” It generally includes all methods of data collection in which each participant responds to the same set of questions in a predetermined order (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:437). In addition, together with a survey strategy, questionnaires are among the most used data collection techniques (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:439). “Questionnaires are often used for descriptive or explanatory research” (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:439). According to Zikmond *et al.* (2013:388), standardised questionnaires need less interviewing skills on the part of the researcher, consume less time, and are simpler for respondents to complete. They allow for better standardisation of reactions.

Therefore, they are very useful to collect truthful information, and easy to analyse because the range of possible answers is limited (Zikmond *et al.*, 2013:388-389).

Designing questions and answer options based on the research objectives utilised to solve the research problems is one of the phases in creating the questionnaire (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015:166-175). The creation of the questionnaire was informed by previous literature and validated by the use of approved questionnaires from previous studies that applied the TPB (Malebana, 2012:389; Liñán & Chen, 2009:601).

In this study, the questionnaire contained six sections numbered from A to E with a total of 42 questions, as indicated below:

- Section A consisted of demographic information. Respondents gave data about their gender, age, work experience, entrepreneurial knowledge and EE (9 questions).
- Section B consisted of questions on EI (8 questions).
- Section C composed of questions on students' ATB (6 questions).
- Section D consisted of questions about SN (6 questions).
- Section E consisted of questions on PBC (9 questions).
- Section F covered questions related to the PEE (4 questions).

The questions in section A used a nominal scale with yes/no responses. All questions in section A, B, C, D, E and F were adopted with no changes from previous EI studies by (Rengiah, 2013:285; Malebana, 2012:389; Liñán & Chen, 2009:612). The key justification for incorporating these questions is that they have been validated in other research studies, which will improve the questionnaire design's reliability. Table 3.1 illustrates the measures used in this study.

Table 3.1: Measures and questionnaire scales

Construct	Author(s)(Year)	Items	Scale
Demographics	Malebana (2014b:1023); Malebana (2012:401)	2	Nominal
Work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge	Malebana (2014b:1023); Malebana (2012:401)	6	Nominal
EE	Malebana (2012:401)	1	Nominal
EI	Malebana (2012:389); Liñán and Chen (2009:612);	8	Likert
ATB	Malebana (2012:389); Liñán and Chen (2009:612);	6	Likert
SN	Malebana (2012:389); Liñán and Chen (2009:612);	6	Likert
PBC	Malebana (2012:389); Liñán and Chen (2009:612);	9	Likert
PEE	Rengiah (2013:285)	4	Likert

Source: Developed by researcher

Demographics, work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge and EE measures were adopted from Malebana (2014b:1023) and Malebana (2012:401). PEE were measured by statements adopted from Rengiah (2013:285). EI, ATB, SN and PBC were measured by statements developed by Malebana (2012:389) and Liñán and Chen (2009:612). Table 3.2 below illustrates questions measuring EI, its antecedents and PEE.

Table 3.2: Questions measuring entrepreneurial intention, its antecedents and PEE

Variables	Questions
EI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur. 2. My professional goal is to become an entrepreneur. 3. I will make every effort to start and run my own business. 4. I am determined to start my own business in the near future. 5. I have very seriously thought of starting a business. 6. I have strong intentions to start a business in the future. 7. I had strong intentions to start my own business before I started with my qualification. 8. My qualification has contributed positively towards my interest to start a business.
ATB	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being an entrepreneur implies more advantages than disadvantages to me. 2. A career as an entrepreneur is totally attractive for me. 3. If I had the opportunity and resources, I would like to start a business. 4. Being an entrepreneur would entail great satisfaction for me. 5. Among various options, I would rather be an entrepreneur. 6. My qualification has contributed positively to my attitude towards becoming an entrepreneur.
SN	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My friends would approve of my decision to start a business. 2. My immediate family would approve of my decision to start a business.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. My fellow classmates would approve of my decision to start a business. 4. My friends value entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers. 5. My immediate family value entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers. 6. My fellow classmates value entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers.
PBC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To start a firm and keep it working would be easy for me. 2. I can control the creation process of a new business. 3. I believe I would be completely able to start a business. 4. I am prepared to do anything to be an entrepreneur. 5. I know all the necessary practical details needed to start a business. 6. If I wanted to, I could easily start and run a business. 7. If I tried to start a business, I would have a high probability of succeeding. 8. It would be very easy for me to develop a business idea. 9. My qualification has provided me with sufficient knowledge to start a business.
PEE	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The subject of entrepreneurship interests me very much because of interactive learning. 2. Entrepreneurship education has taught me to deal with tolerance of uncertainty in the real world. 3. I have a better understanding about business because of entrepreneurship education.

	4. I have developed entrepreneurship skills through the entrepreneurship course.
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Sources: Malebana (2012:389); Liñán and Chen (2009:612); Rengiah (2013:285).

3.5.3.2 Administration of the questionnaire

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016:222) stated that “the ability to obtain both primary and secondary data depends on the researcher gaining access to an appropriate source, or sources where there is a choice.” “The appropriateness of the source usually depends on the research question, related study objective and the research design” (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:222). An online survey questionnaire was carried out using a Google Forms survey. A link was sent to first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students via WhatsApp for them to complete the questionnaire. A consent letter for the respondents was included with the questionnaire, as well as a motivation letter outlining the value of the survey, how to complete it, and how long it would take to finish it. Part taking in the research was completely voluntary.

3.5.3.3 Pilot study

A pilot study is a study that is carried out on a small scale before the major study to ensure that it will be successful (Devisaktsi & Ramayah, 2019:150). The pilot study's sample size could range from 2 to 100 people (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:85). The main purpose of a pilot study is to validate the questionnaire so that the respondents do not encounter any bias in answering all of the questions and to make sure that the questionnaire used in the main study is appropriate (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013:329-360). Previous researchers (Malebana, 2012:389; Liñán & Chen, 2009:612) already tested several questions; accordingly, their research could be perceived as pre-test data. Nevertheless, the questionnaire was pretested with 10 respondents. The respondents in the pilot study consisted of students from the main study's population.

3.5.3.4 Data analysis

Data analysis is “the methods used to analyse the data and describes data handling, preliminary analysis, statistical tests, computer programs, and other technical

information.” (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:510). The data from the questionnaires was captured in Microsoft Excel via a spreadsheet and analysed using SPSS v26 and RStudio. The data was analysed using analytical methods such as descriptive statistics and multivariate statistics. The basic analysis consisted of descriptive analysis, frequency tables and PLS-SEM, as presented in Chapter 4. The sample was summarized using descriptive analysis in terms of demographic characteristics such as age, gender, entrepreneurial knowledge and experience, EE, EI, ATE, SN, PBC, and PEE. Multivariate statistics such as PLS-SEM were used to test the hypothesised structural relationships between the constructs on the given model. The Sobel test was utilised for mediation analysis (see Chapter 4).

SEM is a statistical analysis technique used to analyse structural relationships between latent variables. SEM was performed using the PLS path modelling approach. PLS-SEM as a SEM method, “can model measurement error, can be used to validate measurement models, works well with small sample sizes, provides significance tests regarding the null hypotheses of path coefficients, and is appropriate for exploratory, model building research” (Ravand & Baghaei, 2016:3). The SEM process consists of two components: measurement model evaluation and structural model testing. The purpose of the measurement model evaluation is to evaluate the consistency and accuracy of the manifest variables (Henseler, Ringle & Sinkovics, 2009:298). Consistency evaluations are conducted through individual manifest and construct reliability tests (Hair *et al.*, 2017:112). While validity of the variables is tested based on convergent and discriminant validity, individual manifest reliability explains the variance of the individual manifest relative to latent variable calculating standardised outer loading of the manifest variable (Hair *et al.*, 2017:115; Henseler, Ringle & Sinkovics, 2009:298).

3.6 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Reliability “relates to the consistency of a measure and validity is defined as the extent to which a concept is accurately measured in a quantitative study” (Heale & Twycross, 2015:66). Putka and Sackett (2010:9) indicated that “reliability and validity are concepts that provide the scientific foundation upon which we construct and evaluate predictor and criterion measures of interest.”

3.6.1 Validity of the questionnaire

Bernard (2017:53) referred to validity as “the accuracy and trustworthiness of instruments, data, and findings in research.” The two major types of validity are external and internal validity (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:257). The degree to which scientific research findings can be generalised across people, settings, and times is known as external validity (Cooper & Schindler, 2014:257). Internal validity is concerned with whether the study's questionnaire accurately reflects what the researcher is measuring (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:372). There are different types of internal validity. The sub-sections below provide a detailed description of how validity was achieved.

3.6.1.1 Content and face validity

Face validity, according to Heale and Twycross (2015:66), “deals with how the questionnaire appears to the respondents,” while content validity is a term used to describe “the extent to which a research instrument accurately measures all aspect of a construct.” To achieve face validity, the questionnaire was written in simple English, making it easy for respondents to understand. This was appropriate because most respondents had studied English as an additional or home language prior to tertiary education. Moreover, respondents were only required to select an applicable option, which significantly reduced the time needed to complete the questionnaire. In terms of content validity, the questionnaire covered all the questions related to the components of the study, based on a review of the literature and questionnaires validated by prior EI research papers. This was in accordance with the content validity guidelines provided by Heale and Twycross (2015:66-67).

3.6.1.2 Convergent validity

Convergent validity refers to “the extent to which a measure correlates positively with alternative measures of the same construct” (Hair *et al.*, 2017:112). Convergent validity can be evaluated using the value of average variance extracted (AVE) and the outer loadings of the indicators (Hair *et al.*, 2017:112). Fornell and Larker (1981:377)

mentioned that an adequate convergent validity is achieved when the AVE value of a construct is greater than 0.5. To assess convergent validity, the researcher considered the outer loadings of the indicators and the AVE. The convergent validity results of this study are revealed in section 4.4.1.1.

3.6.1.3 Discriminant validity

Hair *et al.* (2017:115) defined discriminant validity as “the extent to which a construct is truly distinct from other constructs by empirical standards and measures the degree of difference between overlapping constructs.” Cross-loading (Hair *et al.*, 2017:115) and the Fornell-Larcker criterion have long been used by researchers as measures of discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981:376). To achieve discriminant validity, cross-loading was assessed by correlating each latent variable’s component score with other latent variable component scores. Moreover, the Fornell-Larcker criterion was also assessed by comparing the square root of the AVE values with the latent variable correlations. The discriminant validity results of this study are illustrated in Chapter 4.

3.6.2 Internal reliability of the questionnaire

Heale and Twycross (2015:66) stated that “reliability refers to the consistency of a measure.” “It is a necessary contribution to viability, but it is not a sufficient condition for viability.” Reliable tools can be used with the confidence that temporary and indirect factors will not interfere (Cooper & Schindler, 2014: 260). The measurement tool for this study was adopted from previously validated questionnaires on EI with various questions already tested by previous authors (Rengiah, 2013:285; Malebana, 2012:389; Liñán & Chen, 2009:612). Because the research instrument was a self-administered instrument and the researcher did not participate in filling out the questionnaires, self-assessment by the researcher was not possible. When the reliability of the internal consistency of measurements is analysed and evaluated, the true reliability usually lies between cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability (Hair *et al.*, 2017:111). The sub-sections below provide a detailed description of how construct and composite reliability were achieved.

3.6.2.1 Construct reliability

There are different methods of calculating internal consistency, one of the most common being cronbach's alpha (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:451). Cronbach's alpha provides a confidence estimate based on the correlation between the observed indicator variables (Hair *et al.*, 2017:111). The questionnaire utilised within this research comes from previous studies on EI (Rengiah, 2013:285; Malebana, 2012:389; Liñán & Chen, 2009:612). The questions in the questionnaire are based on previous research, which means that it reflects the reality of what the researcher is measuring. This helped ensure that the questionnaire only measured the constructs that were intended to be measured and not those that were not. To achieve construct reliability, the researcher used a cronbach's alpha test to establish whether the research questionnaire accurately measured the same construct operationalised in the validated scale (Taherdoost, 2016b:34). The construct reliability findings of this study are shown within Chapter 4.

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016:451), a cronbach's alpha coefficient value of 0.7 or greater suggests that the scale's combined questions are measuring the same thing. The adopted questionnaire which was used has cronbach's alpha values of 0.926 (Rengiah, 2013:285), 0.818 to 0.940 (Malebana, 2012:417) and 0.773 to 0.943 (Liñán & Chen, 2009:612).

3.6.2.2 Composite reliability

Much like cronbach's alpha, composite reliability is a scale of internal consistency measure. Fornell and Larcker (1981:375) defined composite reliability as an "indicator of shared variance among the observed variable used as an indicator of a latent." "The composite reliability varies between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating higher levels of reliability and is generally interpreted in the same way as cronbach's alpha" (Hair *et al.*, 2017:112). To achieve internal consistency, the researcher used Dillon-Goldstein's rho to measure the internal consistency of constructs. The construct reliability results of this study are shown in section 4.4.1

3.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study was compiled in line with the ethical guidelines specified by the TUT REC. Ethical clearance was sought out from the FCRE and the institution's REC. The following ethical guidelines as outlined by TUT were followed:

- Respondents were advised about the questionnaire's significance and intent, their position in the study, how the information they provided will be used, and their willingness to participate in the study.
- Ethical clearance was obtained from the FCRE and the institution's REC before the research instrument was distributed to students.
- The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were protected during the survey process. All information collected was considered group data and was not disclosed to anyone.
- The data collected during the research process will be stored for at least five years. The dignity and personality of every person involved was always respected, and respondents were not shamed or subjected to any inappropriate behaviour.

3.8 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The primary goal of this chapter was to define the study's research methodology. The research process, objectives, research approach, population and sample, data collection methods, and research reliability and validity were all covered in this chapter. The methods used to collect data were justified and explained. Finally, ethical concerns about the respondent's rights were raised. In Chapter 4, the results of the data analysis are explained.

CHAPTER 4: DATA ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter, the research method used in this study was discussed. This chapter describes the analysis of the data, followed by a discussion of the research results. The results are displayed in tables, graphs and charts. The results are relevant to the research objectives that led the research. The data was analysed to assess the effects of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intentions of entrepreneurship students at TUT. Data was acquired from an online survey questionnaire which was completed by 301 students (n = 301).

As shown in this chapter, descriptive analysis was used to describe the respondents' demographic profile, work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge, entrepreneurship education, and the key variables of this study. SEM was used to test validity, reliability and the hypothesised structural relationships between the constructs in the proposed research model. SEM was performed using the PLS path modelling approach. The Sobel test was used for mediation analysis.

4.2 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS AND OTHER DATA

The target sample for this survey was first, second and third-year students who studied entrepreneurship. These students were full-time students studying towards an undergraduate diploma from TUT. Of the 301 respondents, 44.9% were female, 49.2% were male and about 6% did not disclose their gender. With regard to age, 31.2% were between the ages of 18 and 20, 49.2% were between the ages of 21 and 23 and 25.9% were aged 24 or older. Table 4.1 below illustrates a summary of the demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 4.1: Demographic profile of respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	135	44.9%
	Male	148	49.2%
	Not disclosed	18	6%
	Total	301	100%
Age	18-20 years	94	31.2%
	21-23 years	129	42.9%
	24 and above	78	25.9%
	Total	301	100%

4.2.1 Gender

A total of 148 (49.2%) male respondents and 135 (44.9%) female respondents participated in the study, and 18 (6%) respondents did not disclose their gender. The percentage of male respondents was much higher than the percentage of female respondents. The respondents' gender distribution is shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Gender distribution of respondents

4.2.2 Age

Respondents were asked to choose the most appropriate age group for them by ticking the appropriate option (see Figure 4.2 below). The majority of the respondents were from the age group of 21-23 years old, with 129 (42.9%) respondents, trailed by 94 respondents in the age group of 18-20 years old, representing 31.2% of the study. The minority of the respondents were from the age group of 24 years and above, with 78 (25.9%) respondents. Figure 4.2 below shows the respondents' age distribution.

Figure 4.2: Age distribution of respondents

4.2.3 Work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge of respondents

Of the 301 respondents, 40.5% were currently self-employed (EEK01) and 45.2% had previously been employed (EEK02). About 48% knew successful entrepreneurs in their community (EEK03), 39.9% had family members that were running a business (EEK04) and 43.2% had friends that were running a business (EEK05), while 46.2% had tried to start their own business before (EEK06). The results are summarized in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2: Work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge

Factors of work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge	Frequency	Percentage (%)		Total
		Yes	No	
Work experience				
EEK01	301	40.5	59.5	100
EEK02	301	45.2	54.8	100
Entrepreneurial Knowledge				
EEK03	301	48.2	51.8	100
EEK04	301	39.9	60.1	100
EEK05	301	43.2	56.8	100
EEK06	301	46.2	53.8	100

4.3 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF CONSTRUCT ITEMS

The descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentage, for each independent and dependent variable used in the proposed research model are presented in the below sub-sections. The variables were derived from the entrepreneurial intention model and its antecedents. To achieve the research objective, this section examines respondents' responses to statements related to EE, ATB, SN, PBC and PEE.

4.3.1 Entrepreneurship education

The questionnaire was completed by 301 entrepreneurship students, with approximately 31.2% (94) being first-year students, 34.2% (103) being second-year students, and 34.6% (104) being third-year students. Table 4.3 below shows the respondents' EE distribution.

Table 4.3: Entrepreneurship education at first year, second year and third year

		Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid	First year	94	31.2	31.2	31.2
	Second year	103	34.2	34.2	65.4
	Third year	104	34.6	34.6	100.0
	Total	301	100.0	100.0	

4.3.2 Entrepreneurial intentions

On a five-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), respondents were requested to indicate whether they planned to start a business by answering eight questions on EI (see Appendix B).

The majority of respondents intended to establish their own business in the future, according to the results shown in table 4.4. For instance, approximately 82.4% of the respondents agreed that they “have strong intentions to start a business in the future” (EI6), while 81.4% of respondents also agreed that they “have very seriously thought of starting a business” (EI5). Notably, about 80.4% agreed that they are determined to start their own business in the near future (EI4). Close to 77% of the respondents agreed that their professional goal is to become an entrepreneur (EI2). About 73% agreed that they will make every effort to start and run their own business (EI3). Nearly 70% agreed that their qualification has contributed positively towards their interest to start a business (EI8) and almost 65% of the respondents agreed that they had a strong intentions to start their own business before they started with their qualification” (EI7).

The lowest percentage of agreement was observed for “I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur” (EI1) with 64% of the respondents agreeing, 14.6% disagreeing and 21.3% being unsure. An assessment of the EI of the respondents before they started with their qualifications (EI7, 64.8%) and the contribution of the qualification to the formation of EI (EI8, 69.8%) revealed that the vast majority of students had firm plans to start their own businesses before beginning their studies. Only a 5% increase

in their desire to start their own business was attributed to their exposure to tertiary education. The results showed that being exposed to EE improved the respondents' EI slightly. The results are summarized in Table 4.4 below.

Table 4.4: Entrepreneurial intentions of respondents

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral (unsure)	Agree	Strongly agree	
EI1	301	7.0	7.6	21.3	25.6	38.5	100
EI2	301	1.3	4.7	17.3	23.0	53.8	100
EI3	301	3.7	7.3	16.0	26.3	46.8	100
EI4	301	1.0	6.6	12.0	24.3	56.2	100
EI5	301	2.0	4.0	12.6	23.3	58.1	100
EI6	301	1.7	6.0	10.0	19.9	62.5	100
EI7	301	8.3	9.0	18.0	25.6	39.2	100
EI8	301	2.7	9.6	17.9	31.9	37.9	100

4.3.3 Attitude towards entrepreneurship behaviour

Respondents were requested to indicate the degree to which they favourable or unfavourable the evaluation of being an entrepreneur. The results in Table 4.6 showed that 63.1% of respondents agreed that being an entrepreneur had more advantages than disadvantages (ATB1), while 8.6% of the respondents did not agree and 28.2% were uncertain. Over 66% of respondents agreed that the entrepreneurial profession was very attractive to them (ATB2), compared to 10% who disagreed and 23.6% who were not sure what they thought. About 84% of respondents agreed that, if given the opportunity and resources, they would start a business (ATB3); nevertheless, 5% disagreed with the statement and 11.3% were unsure. Approximately 70% agreed that being an entrepreneur would entail great satisfaction for them (ATB4), while only 7% disagreed with the statement and 22.3% were uncertain. About 63% agreed that, out of several career options, they preferred to be entrepreneurs (ATB5), while 15.3% disagreed and 22.3% were doubtful. Furthermore, 69.1% of the respondents were in agreement with the statement “My qualification has contributed positively to my attitude towards becoming an entrepreneur” (ATB6), while 10.3% disagreed with the

statement and 20.6% were unsure. The results also indicated that most respondents were considering becoming an entrepreneur. This meant that the respondents were most concerned about a good assessment of the entrepreneurial behaviour. If their assessment of starting a business is good, the more likely they are to become entrepreneurs. Table 4.5 summarises these results.

Table 4.5: Respondents’ attitude towards entrepreneurship behaviour

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral (unsure)	Agree	Strongly agree	
ATB1	301	3.7	5.0	28.2	25.9	37.2	100
ATB2	301	2.3	7.6	23.6	31.6	34.9	100
ATB3	301	1.0	4.0	11.3	22.9	60.8	100
ATB4	301	2.3	4.7	22.3	27.7	43.2	100
ATB5	301	4.3	11.0	22.3	23.9	38.5	100
ATB6	301	2.3	8.0	20.6	31.2	37.9	100

4.3.4 Subjective norms

The respondents were requested to show their level of agreement with the statements on what important people would think if they became an entrepreneur by answering six questions on subjective norms (SN1 to SN6, see Appendix B) on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

The results in Table 4.6 revealed that 56% agreed or strongly agreed that their fellow classmates valued entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers (SN6), while close to 29% were unsure. About 55.8% agreed and strongly agreed that their fellow classmates would approve of their decision to start a business (SN3), while 31.6% were hesitant. Notably, more than 53% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their friends would approve of their decision to start a business (SN1), while 26% were unsure. However, close to 47% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their friends valued entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers (SN4), while 31.2% were doubtful. Even though 43.5% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their immediate family would approve of their decision

to start a business (SN2), 31.2% disagreed and 25.3% were unsure. The lowest score of agreement was observed for “My immediate family values entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers”, with 41% of the respondents agreeing, 33% disagreeing and 26.3% being unsure. The results showed that the respondents received little to average social approval and valuation of entrepreneurship from their classmates, friends and family to pursue entrepreneurship as a career.

Table 4.6: Subjective norms of respondents

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral (unsure)	Agree	Strongly agree	
SN1	301	7.6	12.6	25.9	28.6	25.3	100
SN2	301	13.6	17.6	25.3	18.6	24.9	100
SN3	301	5.7	7.0	31.6	31.9	23.9	100
SN4	301	9.0	12.6	31.2	28.6	18.6	100
SN5	301	13.6	19.3	26.3	22.6	18.3	100
SN6	301	3.3	11.6	28.9	32.2	23.9	100

4.3.5 Perceived behavioural control

Section E of the entrepreneurial questionnaire assessed respondents’ agreement or disagreement with statements about perceived behavioural control. Respondents were asked to rate their agreement regarding their ability to start a business on a five-point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree” (see Appendix B). The results in Table 4.7 demonstrated that 81.4% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they would be completely able to start a business (PBC3), while 26.6% were unsure. Around 77% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their qualification had provided them with sufficient knowledge to start a business (PBC9), but 22.3% of the respondents were unsure. Moreover, 77% agreed or strongly agreed that it would be very easy for them to develop a business idea (PBC8), while 13.6% were uncertain. Even though 75.4% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that, if they tried to start a business, they would have a high probability of succeeding (PBC7), 17.6% were unsure. Despite this, close to 71% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they could control the creation process of a new

business (PBC2), while 22% were unsure. In relation to knowing all the necessary practical details needed to start a business (PBC5), 69.2% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed, while 21.6% were hesitant. Notably, approximately 67.5% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they were prepared to do anything to be an entrepreneur (PEE4), 21.6% were unsure and 18% disagreed.

In terms of the first factor of perceived behavioural control (PBC1), roughly 58% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that it would be easy for them to start a business and keep it working, while 24.6% were uncertain and 17.3% disagreed. The lowest level of agreement was observed for “If I wanted to, I could easily start and run a business” (PBC06), with 55.8% agreeing with the statement, 26.3% disagreeing and 17.9% being unsure. The results illustrated a generally positive perception with regard to the respondents’ capability to start a business but indicate doubts surrounding their ability to start a business and keep it working.

Table 4.7: Perceived behavioural control of respondents

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral (unsure)	Agree	Strongly agree	
PBC1	301	3.0	14.3	24.6	26.9	31.2	100
PBC2	301	1.3	6.0	21.9	24.9	45.9	100
PBC3	301	1.7	5.7	11.3	27.6	53.8	100
PBC4	301	4.3	6.6	21.6	26.6	40.9	100
PBC5	301	2.3	7.0	21.6	30.3	38.9	100
PBC6	301	14.3	12.0	17.9	24.6	31.2	100
PBC7	301	2.3	4.7	17.6	28.9	46.5	100
PBC8	301	2.0	7.3	13.6	27.2	49.8	100
PBC9	301	2.3	6.3	22.3	31.2	37.9	100

4.3.6 Perceived effects of entrepreneurship education

Respondents were asked to show the level to which they agreed with the implications for entrepreneurship education on a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (see Appendix B).

The results in Table 4.8 revealed that 80% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they had developed entrepreneurship skills through the entrepreneurship course (PEE4), while 14.3% were unsure. Approximately 78% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they had a better understanding about business because of entrepreneurship education (PEE3), while 15.3% were unsure about this statement. Roughly 70.7% agreed that the subject of entrepreneurship interested them very much because of interactive learning (PEE1), while 21% of the respondents were unsure. The lowest agreement was observed for “Entrepreneurship education has taught me to deal with tolerance of uncertainty in the real world” (PEE2), with 66% of the respondents agreeing and 23.3% being unsure. In summary, these results demonstrated that respondents held a generally favourable perception of entrepreneurship education in relation to developing their entrepreneurial skills to be entrepreneurs or start businesses but expressed doubts in their ability to tolerate the uncertainties of the real world.

Table 4.8: Perceived effects of entrepreneurship education

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
PEE1	301	1.3	7.0	20.9	37.5	33.2	100
PEE2	301	2.7	8.0	23.3	29.9	36.2	100
PEE3	301	1.0	5.7	15.3	38.5	39.5	100
PEE4	301	5.7	4.0	14.3	36.5	43.5	100

4.4 PARTIAL LEAST SQUARES STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING: ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study's analysis was based on Henseler, Ringle, and Sinkovics (2009:298) suggestion of a two-way approach to reporting PLS-SEM findings. Figure 4.3 shows the two-phase PLS-SEM process.

Figure 4.3: Two-phase process of partial least squares path model assessment

Source: Henseler, Ringle and Sinkovics (2009:298)

4.4.1 Measurement model assessment

The PLS-SEM using RStudio was used to analyse the measurement model. For the assessment of the measurement model, factor loadings, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, AVE, convergent validity and discriminant validity were examined.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to evaluate how well grouped indicators measured their corresponding latent construct (Sanchez, 2013:57) and to test the internal consistency among the grouped variables (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016:451). When the Cronbach's alpha is 0.70 or higher, it is accepted in most science research situations as suggesting internal consistency within items. The alpha scores for all the constructs were higher than the minimum cut-off point of 0.7 as recommended by Hair *et al.* (2017:11), indicating internal consistency. In addition, the results in Table 4.9 indicated that the survey questions measured what they were intended to measure and yielded reliable results that could be used for statistical analysis. Dillon-Goldstein's rho coefficient (composite reliability) was used to evaluate the variance of the indicators in the construct of interest, since it is also considered to be a better indicator of internal consistency than Cronbach's alpha because it takes

into account the extent to which the constructs explain their grouped indicators (Sanchez, 2013:58). The Dillon-Goldstein rho coefficients were all above 0.7, which indicated homogeneity among the grouped variables.

4.4.1.1 Convergent validity assessment

The quality of the measurement model was examined here by checking convergent validity, which shows the degree to which the indicators under the constructs are related. Convergent validity was examined by loading the indicator variables onto their respective latent constructs. The loadings were higher than 0.5 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981:376), which suggested a correlation between the latent constructs and their indicators. Most of the loadings were above 0.7 as recommended by Hair *et al.* (2017:115). Only three factors were below 0.7 but above 0.5. The quality of the measurement model was also examined here by checking the AVE, which is an indicator of how much the construct explains the variance of its observed variables (Ravand & Baghei, 2016:8). According to Fornell and Larcker (1981:376), “adequate convergent validity is achieved when the AVE value of a construct is at least 0.5.” All the constructs of this study had AVE values that were above 0.5, indicating adequate convergent validity. Table 4.9 below shows the factor loading, Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability (CR) and AVE values.

Table 4.9: Convergent validity, construct reliability, average variance extracted and composite reliability

Constructs	Question item	Factor Loading	Cronbach’s Alpha	CR	AVE
EE	EE1	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
PEE	PEE1	0.861	0.887	0.922	0.747
	PEE2	0.868			
	PEE3	0.882			
	PEE4	0.846			

ATB	ATB1	0.793	0.884	0.913	0.634
	ATB2	0.847			
	ATB3	0.742			
	ATB4	0.848			
	ATB5	0.809			
	ATB6	0.731			
SN	SN1	0.834	0.889	0.915	0.639
	SN2	0.766			
	SN3	0.799			
	SN4	0.834			
	SN5	0.738			
	SN6	0.820			
PBC	PBC1	0.698	0.904	0.922	0.568
	PBC2	0.784			
	PBC3	0.810			
	PBC4	0.719			
	PBC5	0.836			
	PBC6	0.594			
	PBC7	0.786			
	PBC8	0.797			
	PBC9	0.727			
EI	EI1	0.687	0.913	0.932	0.664
	EI2	0.823			
	EI3	0.866			
	EI4	0.862			
	EI5	0.879			
	EI6	0.886			
	EI7	0.668			

Source: Researcher's own estimates based on survey data

Note: EE = entrepreneurship education, SN = subjective norms, ATB = attitude towards attitude behaviour, PEE = perceived effects of entrepreneurship education, EI = entrepreneurial intention, PBC = perceived behavioural control

4.4.1.2 Discriminant validity assessment

Discriminant validity was utilised to distinguish the constructs' measures from each another. Discriminant validity is a tool which shows how distinct a given construct is from the other constructs (Ravand & Baghei, 2016:8). The distinctiveness of the constructs can be proven by the loyalty of the indicators to their respective latent – each indicator should load higher to its own latent than the others (Hair *et al.*, 2017:112-116). Item EI8 did not load to its own latent and was dropped from the construct to assist the researcher in attaining discriminant validity. Farrell (2010:9) mentioned that, if discriminant validity issues persist, researchers should consider dropping one or more independent variables to attain discriminant validity. The results in Table 4.10 indicated that all the indicators loaded higher on their respective latent construct than the other latent constructs, supporting discriminant validity.

Table 4.10: Cross-loading output

	Item	EE	PEE	ATE	SN	PBC	EI
EE	EE1	1	0.081295	0.099203	0.074346	0.138433	0.186688
	PEE1	0.048979	0.860918	0.698132	0.336398	0.639354	0.62331
PEE	PEE2	0.111682	0.867949	0.613823	0.38298	0.566376	0.562147
	PEE3	0.075438	0.882311	0.580851	0.360292	0.577041	0.552614
	PEE4	0.045838	0.8458	0.566197	0.320097	0.603631	0.552841
	ATB1	0.072805	0.60985	0.792977	0.320029	0.556392	0.673156
ATB	ATB2	0.141895	0.594358	0.847178	0.372349	0.5303	0.707942
	ATB3	0,091121	0.55432	0.742322	0.390577	0.610802	0.706944
	ATB4	0.090259	0.579118	0.847913	0.275405	0.510595	0.581932
	ATB5	0.054942	0.509226	0.808904	0.305537	0.494126	0.556944
	ATB6	-0.00559	0.554524	0.730742	0.251706	0.46722	0.457308
	SN1	0.097805	0.373498	0.410666	0.833892	0.326222	0.447208
SN	SN2	0.020028	0.26911	0.266791	0.766423	0.205047	0.270644
	SN3	0.055737	0.364019	0.350066	0.798449	0.345846	0.345161
	SN4	0.025996	0.36228	0.347963	0.833594	0.320055	0.339014

	SN5	0.018156	0.184664	0.153724	0.737566	0.188946	0.231297
	SN6	0.102695	0.319764	0.328256	0.820316	0.309094	0.360545
PBC	PBC1	0.003913	0.450724	0.503446	0.329455	0.697958	0.465805
	PBC2	0.073523	0.483012	0.414664	0.300495	0.783468	0.488955
	PBC3	0.194278	0.501941	0.516381	0.274841	0.810287	0.583092
	PBC4	0.136913	0.623986	0.657206	0.303929	0.719039	0.579121
	PBC5	0.189773	0.565914	0.58449	0.24958	0.836281	0.577335
	PBC6	0.015625	0.455626	0.450026	0.124026	0.594421	0.332047
	PBC7	0.076038	0.452931	0.402457	0.268798	0.786366	0.515025
	PBC8	0.052966	0.492081	0.4327	0.335663	0.797283	0.562838
	PBC9	0.116979	0.616597	0.513191	0.277836	0.726979	0.459118
EI	EI1	0.133731	0.518757	0.630593	0.236516	0.44699	0.686679
	EI2	0.211754	0.5358	0.685517	0.333843	0.563204	0.823048
	EI3	0.159626	0.577188	0.675478	0.34106	0.579371	0.865549
	EI4	0.193484	0.559174	0.632338	0.400244	0.538486	0.862359
	EI5	0.13416	0.556401	0.646449	0.386804	0.61862	0.879357
	EI6	0.133915	0.5823	0.64474	0.441649	0.624296	0.885864
	EI7	0.087182	0.447885	0.547445	0.295511	0.506405	0.667514

Source: Researcher's own estimates based on survey data

Note: EE = entrepreneurship education, SN = subjective norms, ATB = attitude towards behaviour, PEE = perceived effects of entrepreneurship education, EI = entrepreneurial intentions PBC = perceived behavioural control

The Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to determine discriminant validity. Fornell and Larcker (1981:377) stated that the square root of the AVE for each construct should be greater than the correlations with the other constructs. Table 4.11 below shows that the diagonal values were greater than any correlations between the constructs, confirming the distinct validity of each construct.

Table 4.11: Fornell-Larcker criterion

Constructs	EE	PEE	ATE	SN	PBC	EI
EE	1					
PEE	0.0813	0.8644				
ATB	0.0992	0.7141	0.7964			
SN	0.0743	0.4049	0.4063	0.7989		
PBC	0.1384	0.6914	0.6676	0.3662	0.7535	
EI	0.1867	0.6642	0.7832	0.4313	0.683	0.8146

Note: The diagonal values represent the square root of the AVE for the respective constructs and the off-diagonal values represent the inter-correlation between the respective constructs.

4.4.2 Structural model assessment

The overall objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intentions at the Tshwane University of Technology. In this section, the hypotheses established in section 1.4.3 and emphasised in section 3.3.3 are measured and discussed. The proposed structural model, as indicated in section 1.4.4, was used to determine the model's explanatory power to test the developed hypothesis about the relationship among the constructs. The explanatory power was assessed through the path coefficients and coefficient of determination (R^2).

PLS-SEM using RStudio was utilised to test the hypothesised model that allowed the researcher to test all of the hypotheses. The results in Table 4.12 below indicated that entrepreneurship education had a significant positive relationship with perceived behavioural control ($\beta = 0.083$, $p < 0.05$) and entrepreneurial intentions ($\beta = 0.089$, $p < 0.01$). This meant that, when entrepreneurship education increased, perceived behavioural control and entrepreneurial intentions also increased. No significant relationship was found between subjective norms, attitude towards entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education. The results indicated that the progression of students through entrepreneurship education enhanced their perceived behavioural control. However, the results also indicated that students' advancement through entrepreneurship education did not enhance their attitude towards entrepreneurship

or subjective norms. This suggests that students are more likely to have a higher perceived behavioural control with regard to becoming an entrepreneur when they progress through their academic career.

The results further showed that attitude towards entrepreneurship ($\beta = 0.520$, $p < 0.001$), subjective norms ($\beta = 0.094$, $p < 0.01$) and perceived behavioural control ($\beta = 0.225$, $p < 0.001$) had a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial intentions. This suggests that the three variables of the TPB play a significant role in the formation of entrepreneurial intentions. The results fully supported the TPB as a model for predicting students' entrepreneurial intentions, with attitude towards entrepreneurship having the most significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions, followed by perceived behavioural control and subjective norms. This suggests that the TPB could be considered as a useful framework in analysing students' entrepreneurial intentions at TUT. Furthermore, perceived effects of entrepreneurship education also had a statistically significant positive relationship with attitude towards entrepreneurship ($\beta=0.711$, $p < 0.001$), subjective norms ($\beta=0.401$, $p < 0.001$) and perceived behavioural control ($\beta=0.685$, $p < 0.001$). No significant relationship was found between perceived effects of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions. This suggests that students are more likely to become entrepreneurs when their attitude towards entrepreneurship, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control align with the perceived effects of entrepreneurship education.

Table 4.12: Path coefficients

Relationship	Estimate	Standard error	T-value	p-value
EE → ATB	0.0414	0.0406	1.0200	0.3090
PEE → ATB	0.7110	0.0406	17.5000	0.0000***
EE → SN	0.0417	0.0531	0.7860	0.4330
PEE → SN	0.4010	0.0531	7.5600	0,0000***
EE → PBC	0.0828	0.0417	1,9800	0.0482*
PEE → PBC	0.6850	0.0417	16,4000	0.0000***
EE → EI	0.0894	0.0333	2.6900	0.0077**
PEE → EI	0.0916	0.0522	1.7600	0.0802
ATB → EI	0.5200	0.0507	10.3000	0.0000***

SN → EI	0.0936	0.0368	2.5400	0.0115**
PBC → EI	0.2250	0.0490	4.6100	0.0000***

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

The coefficient of determination (R^2) was employed in the measurement of the model's predictive power and is calculated as the squared correlation between a specific endogenous construct's actual and predicted values. Hair *et al.* (2017:198) considered R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 for the dependent variables as substantial, moderate and weak, respectively. As illustrated in Table 4.13 below, the results show that EI had an R^2 value of 0.679. This means that PEE, SN, PBC, EE and ATB accounted for 68% of the variation in EI. According to Hair *et al.* (2017:198), this could be considered as moderate. ATB had an R^2 value of 0.512, which means that EE and PEE explained 51.2% of the variance in ATB. This could also be considered as moderate (Hair *et al.*, 2017:198). SM had an R^2 value of 0.166, which means that EE and PEE explained 17% of the variation in SN. According to Hair *et al.* (2017:198), this could be considered as weak. PBC had an R^2 value of 0.485, which means that EE and PEE accounted for 49% of variance in PBC. This could also be considered as weak according to Hair *et al.* (2017:198).

Table 4.13: Coefficient of determination (R^2)

CONSTRUCT	MARY INNER M	ODEL
	Type	R^2
EE	Exogenous	0
PEE	Exogenous	0
ATB	Endogenous	0.512
SN	Endogenous	0.166
PBC	Endogenous	0.485
EI	Endogenous	0.679

Source: Researcher's own estimates based on survey data

The statistically significant level is often expressed as a p -value that is between 0 and 1 (Dahiru, 2008:22). The smaller the p -value, the stronger the indication that the null hypothesis should be rejected. A p -value of less than ($<$) 0.05 is statistically significant and indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis. In that instance, the null

hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. However, a p -value that is greater than ($>$) 0.05 is regarded as not statistically significant and indicates strong evidence for accepting the null hypothesis. As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

The findings of this research suggested that the construct of EE had a statistically significant positive relationship with PBC and EI. As a result, hypotheses **H₁** and **H₄** were accepted at a $p < 0.05$ significance level, and **H₂** and **H₃** were rejected at a $p > 0.05$ significance level. Null hypotheses **H₀₂** and **H₀₃** were retained, while **H₀₁** and **H₀₄** were rejected. Table 4.14 and Figure 4.4 below illustrate the summary of the hypothesis test and this study's structural model.

Table 4.14: Summary of hypothesis test

Hypothesised path	Hypothesis	Path coefficient	Standard error	T-value	p -value	R ²	Level of significance
EE → EI	H ₁	0.0894	0.0333	2.6900	0.0077	0.679	**
EE → ATB	H ₂	0.0414	0.0406	1.0200	0.3090	0.512	n.s.
EE → SN	H ₃	0.0417	0.0531	0.7860	0.4330	0.166	n.s.
EE → PBC	H ₄	0.0828	0.0417	1.9800	0.0482	0.485	*

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Figure 4.4: Structural model

Source: Researcher's compilation based on study results

4.4.3 Mediation analysis

According to Ozdil and Kutlu (2019:31), “the concept of mediation is used to indicate that the effect of one or more independent variables are transferred by a third variable to a dependent variable.” Koopman, Howe and Hollenback (2014:241) recommended using the Sobel test over bootstrapping to determine the strength and significance of mediation analysis. Ozdil and Kutlu (2019:30) mentioned that the “Sobel test yields less erroneous results in larger samples while bootstrapping produces more reliable results in smaller samples.” Koopman, Howe and Hollenback (2014:242) alluded that researchers should be wary of bootstrapping in contexts involving indirect effects with medium or larger samples and recommended using the Sobel test over bootstrapping when the sample size exceeds 140 cases. In light of this, this study adopted the Sobel test mediation analysis approach to determine whether ATB, SN and PBC mediated the effects of EE and PEE on EI.

The results indicated that PBC ($\beta = 0.0186$, $p < 0.05$) mediated the relationship between EE and EI. This was a partial mediation because EE had a significant direct effect on EI. ATB ($\beta = 0.0022$, $p > 0.05$) and SN ($\beta = 0.0039$, $p > 0.05$) were insignificant in mediating the relationship between EE and EI, with a significance level of $p > 0.05$. In addition, the results further revealed that ATB ($\beta = 0.3697$, $p < 0.001$), SN ($\beta = 0.0375$, $p < 0.01$) and PBC ($\beta = 0.1541$, $p < 0.001$) mediated the relationship between PEE and EI. This was a full mediation because PEE had an insignificant direct effect on EI. Table 4.15 below shows the summary of the results.

Table 4.15: Mediation results

Hypothesized path	Direct relationship	Indirect relationship	<i>p</i> -value	Mediation
EE → ATB → EI	0.0414	0.0022	0.468	n.s
EE → SN → EI	0.0417	0.0039	0.335	n.s
EE → PBC → EI	0.0828	0.0186	0.034	Partial mediation
PEE → ATB → EI	0.7110	0.3697	0.000	Full mediation
PEE → SN → EI	0.4010	0.0375	0.008	Full mediation
PEE → PBC → EI	0.6850	0.1541	0.000	Full mediation

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

4.5 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter focused on data analysis and the presentation of the findings. Statistical analysis of data was performed using descriptive statistics and PLS-SEM.

The PLS-SEM results revealed that EE had a statistically significant effect on PBC and EI. The positive effect of EE on EI was mediated by PBC. It was also found that EE did not have a statistically significant effect on ATB or SN. In addition, the PEE had a positive relationship with ATB, SN and PBC, but had no statistically significant effect on the EI. The positive effect of EE on EI was conveyed through ATB, SN and PBC. This study's recommendations and conclusions are presented in the following chapter.

CHAPTER 5: RECOMMENDATIONS, LIMITATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 1 presented the background, objectives, hypotheses, research model and research methodology of the study. Chapter 2 discussed the concept of entrepreneurship, EE, and the role and value of EE in the entrepreneurial process. Two models of EI, namely, the EEM and the TPB, were also discussed, along with their antecedents. Empirical findings of studies which examined effects of EE using TPB were also discussed. Chapter 3 outlined the methodology of the study, and discussed and justified data collection methods. The findings of this research were presented and interpreted in Chapter 4.

The conclusions drawn from the research findings are outlined in this chapter. The conclusions are centred on the primary objective, research problem and results of this study. The implications of these findings and resulting suggestions for future research are also explained. Implications are drawn from the conclusions and the objectives of this study.

5.2 BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

In light of the unemployment difficulties that the South African youth is currently experiencing, there has been pressure on EE to provide a pathway out of poverty and reduce the youth unemployment rate, which currently stands at 61.3% (Statistics South Africa, 2020:15). Hence, EE is important to employment creation and the growth of the economy. The high unemployment rate clearly shows that, compared to other countries, there is low entrepreneurship activity among South African citizens (Chimucheka, 2014:404). Moses *et al.* (2016:645) stated that the value of EE for entrepreneurship cannot be overemphasised due to the advantages it holds for employment creation and growth of the economy. According to the TPB, intentions to start a business is determined by ATB, SN and PBC (Ajzen, 2012:445; 2011:1117). These intentions, together with PBC, account for considerable variance in actual behaviour (Ajzen, 2012:450). This study examined, based on the TPB, the effects of

EE on the intentions of students at TUT to start a business. The study's primary and secondary objectives, as well as its hypotheses, are detailed below.

5.2.1 Primary objective

As formally stated in Chapter 1, the overall aim of this study was to assess the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT.

5.2.2 Secondary objectives

The following secondary objectives were developed to help achieve the primary objectives of this research:

- To assess if EE has a significant impact on students' EI.
- To determine the impact of EE on students' ATB.
- To establish the impact of EE on students' SN.
- To assess the impact EE has on students' PBC.

5.2.3 Hypotheses

Based on the study's objectives, the following hypotheses were developed:

H₀₁: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' EI.

H₁: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' EI.

H₀₂: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.

H₂: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.

H₀₃: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' SN.

H₃: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' SN.

H₀₄: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.

H₄: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.

5.3 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

A summary of the research findings in relation to the primary objective, secondary objectives, hypotheses, and proposed research model is presented in this section.

5.3.1 Respondents' demographic profile

Respondents of this study consisted of 301 first, second and third-year students from TUT. These students were found using convenience sampling as outlined in section 3.4.2.2. The main reason for using these respondents was because their course focuses on providing students with the needed entrepreneurial skills and knowledge required to establish and develop a new business venture from the first year of study all the way through to the last year of study. Moreover, entrepreneurship students are expected to seek gainful employment or start businesses during the course or soon after graduation. As a result, it was appropriate to study the effects of EE on students' EI, ATB, PBC and SN. The respondents demographic profile is summarized below.

5.3.1.1 Gender distribution

Majority (49.2%) of the respondents were male, 44.9% were female and 6% did not disclose their gender (see Figure 4.1).

5.3.1.2 Age distribution

The data on the respondents' ages indicated that 31.2% were between 18 and 20 years old, 42.9% were between 21 and 23 years old, and 25.9% were 24 years old or older (see Figure 4.2).

5.3.1.3 Distribution of respondents by entrepreneurship education

Data on EE indicated that 31.2% of the respondents were first-year students, 34.2% were in their second year and 34.6% were in their third year of study (see Figure 4.3).

5.3.1.4 Distribution of the respondents by experience and entrepreneurial knowledge

The findings on the work experience and entrepreneurial knowledge of entrepreneurship students at TUT illustrated that 40.5% of respondents were self-employed, 45.2% had been employed before, 48.2% knew successful entrepreneurs in their community, 39.9% had family members who were running a business and 43.2% had friends who were running a business, while 46.2% of respondents had tried to start a business before.

5.3.2 Results for the proposed model of the effects of entrepreneurship education

As outlined in section 1.4, this section discusses the findings in relation to the proposed research model, study hypotheses, and secondary research objectives.

The purpose of this section is to report on the results of the secondary objectives. Based on the TPB, four hypotheses were tested to examine the effects of EE in influencing students' EI at TUT, namely, EE, ATB, SN, PBC and EI. A model of EI, which was based on the TPB, was proposed in section 1.4.4. The findings showed that EE had a significant relationship with two variables of the TPB, namely, PBC and EI. In relation to the results discussed in the subsections below, the TPB plays an important role in the formation of students' EI.

5.3.2.1 Relationship between entrepreneurship education and the antecedents of entrepreneurial intentions

PLS-SEM was used to evaluate the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT. The findings of the PLS-SEM revealed that EE had a statistically significant relationship with PBC and EI. The results further uncovered that EE had no statistically significant relationship with ATB and SN. These findings suggest that EE does not significantly influence students' SN and ATB, but has a statistically significant positive influence on their EI and perceptions with regards to their capabilities to launch a business. These outcomes are in support of prior research which discovered that EE is statistically

significantly related to PBC and EI (Otache *et al.*, 2019:14; Wahjono, Marina & Fen, 2019:263-265; Ebewo, Rugimbana & Shambare, 2017:287; Feder & Nițu-Antonie, 2017:98; Ndofirepi & Rambe, 2017:196; Sun *et al.*, 2017:1382-1383; Entrialgo & Iglesias, 2016:1221-1225; Karimi *et al.*, 2016b:195-199; Iglesias Sánchez *et al.*, 2016:220; Ajike *et al.*, 2015:128-130; Murugesan & Jayavelu, 2015:269; Prabandari & Sholihab, 2015:389; Rauch & Hulsink, 2015:195-198; Küttim *et al.*, 2014:665; Karali, 2013:34). This included studies conducted in SA which discovered that EE had a statistically positive correlation with EI (Marire & Dhurup, 2018:200-201; Marire, 2015:66).

On the other hand, the study outcomes contradicted the outcomes of some of previous studies which discovered that EE had a statistically significant and positive relationship with ATB and SN (Paray & Kumar, 2020:61-66; Otache *et al.*, 2019:14; Wahjono, Marina & Fen, 2019:263-265; Badr *et al.*, 2018:219; Ndofirepi & Rambe, 2017:196; Sun *et al.*, 2017:1382-1383; Ajike *et al.*, 2015:128-130; Küttim *et al.*, 2014:665; Karali, 2013:34). Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it was concluded that EE had a statistically significant relationship with the PBC and EI. Therefore, hypotheses **H₁** and **H₄** were confirmed by the results of the research. Consequently, the relationship between EE, PBC, and EI was found to be statistically significant.

5.3.2.2 Relationship between perceived effects of entrepreneurship education and the antecedents of entrepreneurial intentions

PLS-SEM was used to test whether the PEE had a significant effect on ATB, SN, PBC and EI. The results revealed that the PEE had a positive and statistically significant relationship with ATB, SN and PBC, but no statistically significant direct effect on EI. This suggests that students are more likely to become entrepreneurs when their ATB, SN and PBC align with their PEE. Hence, the relationship between the PEE and EI was fully mediated by ATB, SN and PBC. This was a full mediation because the PEE had an insignificant direct effect on students' EI. The results of this study contradicted the findings of Rengiah (2013:208), who discovered that PEE (entrepreneurial curricula) had a direct and statistically significant relationship with EI.

5.3.2.3 Relationship between attitude towards behaviour, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and entrepreneurial intentions

This section reports on findings surrounding the TPB and its ability to predict the EI of first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students at TUT. The PLS-SEM results indicated that ATB, SN and PBC had a statistically significant and positive relationship with students' EI. The results were in full support of the TPB as a model for predicting students' EI. This suggests that the three variables of the TPB played an important role in the formation of EI of the respondents and could be considered as a useful framework in analysing students' EI at TUT.

The findings showed that all the three variables were statistically significant, with ATB scoring the highest beta value, followed by the PBC and SN. These findings are in line with those of previous research that fully supported the TPB as a model for predicting EI (Aga & Singh, 2020:2383; Alshebami *et al.*, 2020:3610; Ilman, Ananda & Pohan, 2020:1273-1275; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2020:204; Feola *et al.*, 2019:1433-1436; Feder & Nițu-Antonie, 2017:98; Mwiya *et al.*, 2017:602; Tarek, 2017:79; Tarek, 2016:350; Hussain & Norashdah, 2015:49; Kautonen, van Gelderen & Fink, 2015:666; Pulka, Aminu & Rikwentishe, 2015:154; Zapkau *et al.*, 2015:645; Mahmoud & Muharam, 2014:21; Schlaegel & Koenig, 2014:306). This included research on the TPB done in SA which found that ATB, SN and PBC were statistically significantly related to EI (Mothibi & Malebana, 2019:8; Mothibi, 2018:78; Urban & Chantson, 2019:967; Marire & Dhurup, 2018:200-201; Malebana, 2014a:137).

Nonetheless, the findings of this study contradicted those of some previous TPB studies, which found that SN were not statistically significantly related to EI and thus did not contribute to the TPB's predictive ability (Alshebami *et al.*, 2020:3610; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2020:204; Paiva *et al.*, 2019:16; Wibowo, 2019:7; Awan & Ahmad, 2017:24-25; Marire, Mafini & Dhurup, 2017:27; Buli & Yesuf, 2015:899). This included studies that were conducted in SA which revealed that SN were not statistically significantly related to EI (Davids, 2017:48; Marire, 2015:66). Moreover, the results contradicted previous studies which detected that ATB was not statistically significantly related to EI (Bhinekawati, Nelloh & Abdurahman, 2020:90-91).

5.3.2.4 Conclusions on the research model, research objective and hypotheses

The TPB was adopted in this research to evaluate the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT. The research model incorporated the research objectives and hypotheses, which, when examined, provided evidence for the support, rejection or modification of the proposed research model. Section 1.4.4 discussed the initial research model, which was revised following the hypothesis testing. Figure 5.1 below illustrates the revised research model, and Table 5.1 gives a summary of the research objectives, hypotheses and findings. From the outcomes, EE is seen to influence PBC and EI, while PEE are observed to stimulate EI through PBC, ATB and SN.

Figure 5.1: Revised research model

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Source: Researcher's own compilation based on study results

Table 5.1: Research objectives, hypotheses and findings

Primary objective: To evaluate the effects of EE on students' EI at TUT		
Research objective	Hypotheses	Findings
To assess if EE has a significant impact on students' EI.	<p>H₀₁: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' EI.</p> <p>H₁: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' EI.</p>	EE had a significant positive relationship with students' EI.
To determine the impact of EE on students' ATB.	<p>H₀₂: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.</p> <p>H₂: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' ATB.</p>	EE had an insignificant effect on students' ATB.
To establish the impact of EE on students' SN.	<p>H₀₃: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' SN.</p> <p>H₃: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' SN.</p>	EE had an insignificant effect on students' SN.
To assess the impact EE has on students' PBC.	<p>H₀₄: EE has no statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.</p> <p>H₄: EE has a statistically significant relationship with students' PBC.</p>	EE had a significant positive effect on students' PBC.

5.4 IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

Unemployment among young people has a clear negative impact on economic growth and productivity. The number of unemployed graduates in SA is unprecedented and requires immediate attention. In the GEM report, Herrington, Kew and Mwanga (2017:7) indicated that the percentage of 18–24 year olds in SA engaged in early-stage entrepreneurial activity is significantly lower than the African average, which is nearly double the South African figure at 11%. Additionally, with SA's high youth unemployment figure now at 61.3% (Statistics South Africa, 2020:15), this is a cause for concern. The focal point of this study lay in detecting the effects of EE on students' intentions to establish their own business and what specific strategies aimed at uplifting students to establish a new business can be cultivated.

The findings of the study have implications that can be used to guide entrepreneurship educators and TUT's DME. Both PBC and EI must be improved in order to improve the effects of EE. According to the findings, EE had a significant and positive impact on students' PBC and EI. These findings suggest that there is a need for the DME to convey more information about support programmes which are accessible for those who want to be entrepreneurs and how to gain access to such programmes. Conveying such information may impact positively on students' PBC and their intentions to become entrepreneurs. Tiwari *et al.* (2019:13) suggested that universities should organise more entrepreneurship-related activities and programmes to enhance students' interest in entrepreneurial activities. Mothibi (2018:127) recommended using media platforms to create awareness of support programmes that currently exist for entrepreneurial students.

This study also has implications for entrepreneurship educators. In order to enhance PBC and EI among entrepreneurship students, entrepreneurship educators should supplement their teaching with the use of local entrepreneurs as guest speakers and entrepreneurial seminars. Local entrepreneurs as guest speakers can show students that the topics they are learning about are imperative to know and can share their experience with them. Entrepreneurial seminars attract highly specialised and knowledgeable speakers. There are very few other training methods that offer the same opportunity to hear the opinions of entrepreneurship professionals or to ask

those professionals to contribute to business challenges. This may result in raised perceptions regarding behavioural control and students' intentions to start a business and keep it running. Entrepreneurship educators should also incorporate content that is aimed at informing students about the support programmes which are available to them. This kind of content may also improve students' PBC and their intentions to start a business, and may increase their knowledge of how to gain access to support programmes. Walter and Block (2016:219) mentioned that the more entrepreneurial knowledge and motivation individuals receive from EE, the more confident they will be in overcoming regulatory barriers and engaging in entrepreneurial behaviour.

5.5 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

As with other studies, this study had limitations that warrant future research. A summary of the limitations encountered during the research process is provided below:

- This research only considered first, second and third-year students studying entrepreneurship at TUT and therefore cannot be generalised or be considered to be representative of all first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students in SA.
- The sample of this study consisted of students pursuing an undergraduate entrepreneurship course at TUT. This research did not consider the views of students pursuing other programmes at TUT. The findings of this study were limited to the views of first, second and third-year entrepreneurship students.
- To address the research problem, this study used a quantitative research approach, which has both advantages and disadvantages. Some of these limitations could be addressed by using a mixed method research approach, in which a qualitative research approach, rather than quantitative data alone, could be used to obtain relevant personal views of the proposed sample.
- The main limitation of this research lay in the use of cross-sectional data. Students were only observed at one point in time and not across time. A longitudinal research study could provide a more in-depth analysis in addressing this study's research problem.

- This study only made use of the TPB model to explore the effects of EE on students' EI. Deeper insights could be generated using a combination of the TPB and the EEM.

5.6 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

To solve the research problem, the following nuance have been identified for future research:

- Researchers should consider longitudinal research to evaluate the effects of EE on students' EI in the South African context.
- Future studies should consider integrating the TPB and EEM to predict the effects of EE on students' EI in the South African context.
- Future scholars should consider conducting a similar study in other South African universities that offer EE as a course in order to generalise the outcomes of this study.
- Scholars should consider making use of a mixed method research approach, in which a qualitative research approach could be used to acquire relevant personal views of the proposed sample as opposed to using quantitative data alone. This could result in a more in-depth analysis of the research topic.

5.7 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The main aim of this chapter was to come to conclusions based on the research findings and analysis. The context, objectives, hypotheses and research model of this study were also discussed in this chapter. Research results were defined, interpreted and linked to previous research studies. Based on the results of this research, implications for policymakers and entrepreneurship educators were also identified. Limitations of the study were also presented, along with suggestions for future research.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Permission for using the questionnaire

RE: Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire

From: Francisco Liñán <flinan@us.es>
Sent: Friday, February 21, 2020 11:34:50 AM
To: S Mahlaole <214001365@tut4lifeac.onmicrosoft.com>
Subject: Re: Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire

Dear Simon,

Thank you for your interest in our work.

Please find attached 3 versions of the EIQ and the papers in which they were used. The first versions (EIQ2 and EIQ3) are designed as aggregated scales. The papers in which they were used are Liñán & Chen (2009) and Liñán, Urbano & Guerrero (2011), respectively.

More recently, within the VIE Project (<http://institucional.us.es/vie>), we have developed a newer and more refined questionnaire. In it, Personal Attitude and Subjective Norm has been measured by pondering personal beliefs with the relevance attached to each belief. I attached this newer version of the questionnaire (Original in Spanish, the translation made by ourselves), and one of the papers in which it was used (Liñán, Moriano & Jaén, 2016). You can use them as you feel is best, but do please acknowledge your source.

Best regards,

Francisco Liñán

Professor in Entrepreneurship and Innovation

Anglia Ruskin University. School of Management. Cambridge. francisco.linan@anglia.ac.uk

Universidad de Sevilla. Depto. Economía Aplicada I. Sevilla. flinan@us.es

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Francisco_Linan

<https://es.linkedin.com/in/franciscolinan>

Selected Publications:

Nabi, G., Walmsley, A., Liñán, F., Akhtar, I., & Neame, C. (2018). Does entrepreneurship education in the first year of higher education develop entrepreneurial intentions? The role of learning and inspiration. *Studies in Higher Education*, 43(3), 452–467.

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[Reply](#) | [Reply all](#) | [Forward](#)

Appendix B: Questionnaire

Tshwane University
of Technology

We empower people

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT AND
ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Dear Student

Thank you for taking your time to participate in this research. This questionnaire is part of a study designed to examine the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' intentions to start a business. The questionnaire should only take up to 15-20 minutes of your time. Your cooperation is much appreciated.

Purpose of the Survey:

This study seeks to evaluate the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intentions at the Tshwane University of Technology. Your participation in this study will contribute towards understanding the entrepreneurship process and determining the extent to which entrepreneurship education is effective in influencing students' intentions to start a business.

General Instructions:

Before you begin, make sure you understand the following instructions:

- When evaluating the questions, please provide responses from your own perspective, as honestly as possible
- Please respond to the items (or questions) by making a tick (x) what you consider to be the answer, or filling in the blanks.
- Please complete all sections, and do not leave any question unanswered
- You are requested to apply the scale provided for each of the questions.
- Please note that your name is not required nor is it requested, hence confidentiality is assured.

I would like to convey my utmost gratitude and appreciation for your participation in this study!

Thank you

Mr. Simon Thabo Mahlaole
Tshwane University of Technology

Survey adapted from: Liñán and Chen (2009:612) and Malebana (2012:424-459)
Please see questionnaire on the next page

THE EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION ON STUDENTS' ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS AT THE TSHWANE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

SECTION A: GENERAL DEMOGRAPHICS

Instructions: Please respond to the following questions by placing a check mark (√) in the answer box that corresponds with your response to the question or statement.

DEMOGRAPHICS

GD1. Indicate your gender.

Male	1
Female	2
Not disclose	3

GD2. Please indicate your age group.

18 – 20	1
21– 23	2
24 - above	3

WORK EXPERIENCE

EEK1. Are you currently self-employed?

Yes	1
No	2

EEK2. Have you ever been employed before?

Yes	1
No	2

ENTREPRENEURIAL KNOWLEDGE

EEK3. Do you know any successful entrepreneurs in your community?

Yes	1
No	2

EEK4. Are any of your family members running a business?

Yes	1
No	2

EEK5. Are any of your friends running a business?

Yes	1
No	2

EEK6. Have you ever tried to start a business before?

Yes	1
No	2

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

EE1. At which level of study are you currently studying entrepreneurship?

First year	1
Second year	2
Third year	3

SECTION B: ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS

Below are statements describing your situation on your intentions to create a business.

Instructions: Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.
(1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree)

EI1	I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur.	1	2	3	4	5
EI2	My professional goal is to become an entrepreneur.	1	2	3	4	5
EI3	I will make every effort to start and run my own business.	1	2	3	4	5
EI4	I am determined to start my own business in the near future.	1	2	3	4	5
EI5	I have very seriously thought of starting a business.	1	2	3	4	5
EI6	I have strong intentions to start a business in the future.	1	2	3	4	5
EI7	I had a strong intentions to start my own business before I started with my qualification.	1	2	3	4	5
EI8	My qualification has contributed positively towards my interest to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5

SECTION C: ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURSHIP BEHAVIOUR

Below are statements on the degree to which you favourable or unfavourable the evaluation of being an entrepreneur.

Instructions: Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.
(1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree)

ATB1	Being an entrepreneur implies more advantages than disadvantages to me.	1	2	3	4	5
ATB2	A career as an entrepreneur is totally attractive for me.	1	2	3	4	5
ATB3	If I had the opportunity and resources, I would like to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5
ATB4	Being an entrepreneur would entail great satisfactions for me.	1	2	3	4	5
ATB5	Among various options, I would rather be an entrepreneur.	1	2	3	4	5
ATB6	My qualification has contributed positively to my attitude towards becoming an entrepreneur.	1	2	3	4	5

SECTION D: SUBJECTIVE NORM

Below are statements on what important people would think if you become an entrepreneur.

Instructions: Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.
(1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree)

SN1	My friends would approve of my decision to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5
SN2	My immediate family would approve of my decision to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5
SN3	My fellow classmates would approve of my decision to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5
SN4	My friends value entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers.	1	2	3	4	5
SN5	My immediate family value entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers.	1	2	3	4	5
SN6	My fellow classmates value entrepreneurial activities above other activities and careers.	1	2	3	4	5

SECTION E: PERCEIVED BEHAVIORAL CONTROL

To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding your entrepreneurial capacity?

Instructions: Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.
(1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree)

PBC1	To start a firm and keep it working would be easy for me.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC2	I can control the creation process of a new business.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC3	I believe I would be completely able to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC4	I am prepared to do anything to be an entrepreneur.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC5	I know all the necessary practical details needed to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC6	If I wanted to, I could easily start and run a business.	1	2	3	4	5

PBC7	If I tried to start a business, I would have a high probability of succeeding.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC8	It would be very easy for me to develop a business idea.	1	2	3	4	5
PBC9	My qualification has provided me with sufficient knowledge to start a business.	1	2	3	4	5

SECTION F: PERCEIVED EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding entrepreneurship education?

Instructions: Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.
(1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree)

PEE1	The subject of entrepreneurship interests me very much because of interactive learning.	1	2	3	4	5
PEE2	Entrepreneurship education has taught me to deal with tolerance of uncertainty in the real world.	1	2	3	4	5
PEE3	I have a better understanding about business because of entrepreneurship education.	1	2	3	4	5
PEE4	I have developed entrepreneurship skills through the entrepreneurship course.	1	2	3	4	5

THE END!

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY

Appendix C: Information Leaflet

**Tshwane University
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FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

**DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT
AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP**

INFORMATION LEAFLET AND INFORMED CONSENT

PROJECT TITLE: THE EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION ON STUDENTS' ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS AT THE TSHWANE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

Primary investigator: Mr ST Mahlaole, B Tech (Sport Management)

Study leader: Dr MJ Malebana, D Com, Department of Management and Entrepreneurship, Tshwane University of Technology, Polokwane

Dear Potential Research Participant,

You are invited to participate in a research study that forms part of my formal M Tech-studies. This information leaflet will help you to decide if you would like to participate. Before you agree to take part, you should fully understand what is involved. You should not agree to take part unless you are completely satisfied with all aspects of the study.

WHAT IS THE STUDY ALL ABOUT?

Entrepreneurship educations can play a vital role in developing the culture of entrepreneurship in South Africa. Investigating the effects of entrepreneurship education could assist the efforts to promote entrepreneurship in South Africa. In addition, the results of this study may help policy makers determine the extent to which entrepreneurship education is effective in influencing intentions of students to become

entrepreneurs.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine based on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' intentions to start a business at the Tshwane University of Technology.

WHAT WILL YOU BE REQUIRED TO DO IN THE STUDY?

A structured online survey questionnaire will be used in this study. The questionnaire should take approximately 15-20 minutes to complete it.

If you decide to participate in this study, you will be required to do the following:

- To give informed consent using an online survey questionnaire that you agree to participate in the study.
- To complete an online survey questionnaire related to effects of entrepreneurship education on student's entrepreneurial intentions at Tshwane University of Technology.
- You will be asked to respond to questions regarding the effects of entrepreneurship educations on students' intentions to start a business at Tshwane University of Technology.
- Moreover, you will be required to complete the questionnaire individually and submit it electronically upon completion. Students' (Respondents) will be given a week to complete the online survey questionnaire before responses can be tallied and results analysed.

ARE THERE ANY CONDITIONS THAT MAY EXCLUDE YOU FROM THE STUDY?

You will not be eligible to participate in this study if you are not a registered student at the Tshwane University of Technology studying Entrepreneurship as a course within the Department of Management and Entrepreneurship at first, second or third-year level of study.

CAN ANY OF THE STUDY PROCEDURES RESULT IN PERSONAL RISK, DISCOMFORT OR INCONVENIENCE?

Questionnaires: The study and procedures involve no foreseeable physical discomfort or inconvenience to you or your family. Due to the personal nature of the questions, you may experience some emotional discomfort.

Minimal risk/discomfort/inconvenience: Participation in the study involves minimal risks, discomforts and/or inconveniences that are no more than the risks, discomforts and/or inconveniences one encounter in daily living.

WHAT ARE THE POTENTIAL BENEFITS THAT MAY COME FROM THE STUDY?

The benefits of participating in this study are:

- You will make a contribution towards facilitating entrepreneurial mind-set and encouraging self-employment,
- You will make a contribution towards entrepreneurship education's efforts to create opportunities, ensure social justice and stimulating the economy of South Africa.
- You as a student along with your department will be sent the finding of the research presented by the researcher.

WILL YOU RECEIVE ANY FINANCIAL COMPENSATION OR INCENTIVE FOR PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY?

You will not be financially compensated or receive any incentive for participation in the study.

WHAT ARE YOUR RIGHTS AS A PARTICIPANT IN THIS STUDY?

Your participation in this study is voluntary. You have the right to withdraw at any stage without any penalty or future disadvantage whatsoever and you do not even have to provide the reasons/s for your decision. Your withdrawal will in no way influence the research team.

HOW WILL CONFIDENTIALITY AND ANONYMITY BE ENSURED IN THE STUDY?

All information obtained during the course of this study is strictly confidential. The study data will be coded so that it will not be linked to your name. Your identity will not be revealed while the study is being conducted or when the study is reported in scientific journals. All the data sheets that have been collected will be stored in a secure place. Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. The information received during the project will only be used for research purposes and not be released for any academic assessment, study progress, disciplinary purposes and/or study permit-related matters.

IS THE RESEARCHER QUALIFIED TO CARRY OUT THE STUDY?

The researcher is an adequately trained and qualified researcher in the study fields covered by this research project. He has completed a course in research methodology and is fully equipped to conduct the research under the supervision of Dr. Malebana.

HAS THE STUDY RECEIVED ETHICAL APPROVAL?

Yes. The Faculty Committee for Postgraduate Studies, Faculty Committee for Research Ethics and the Research Ethics Committee of the Tshwane University of Technology have approved the formal study proposal (REC Reference number: REC2020-11-010). In addition, the office of the deputy registrar has granted written approval to for the study. Nevertheless, the study will be conducted according to internationally accepted ethical principles.

WHO CAN YOU CONTACT FOR ADDITIONAL INFORMATION REGARDING THE STUDY?

The primary investigator, Mr ST Mahlaole, can be contacted at any time on cellular phone at 0796502938.

The study leader, Dr MJ Malebana, can be contacted during office hours on Monday and Friday at Tel (015) 287 0202 or e-mail: malebanamj@tut.ac.za

Should you have any questions regarding the ethical aspects of the study, you can contact the chairperson of the TUT Research Ethics Committee, Dr H Mason, during office hours at Tel (012) 382-5073, E-mail MasonH@tut.ac.za. Alternatively, you can report any serious unethical behaviour at the University's Toll Free Hotline 0800 21 23 41.

DECLARATION: CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This research study was funded by the Tshwane University of Technology and services seta. No publication prohibitions, conditions or limitations were placed on the researcher.

A FINAL WORD

Your co-operation and participation in the study will be greatly appreciated. Please indicate on the online survey questionnaire if you agree to participate in the study.

CONSENT

I hereby confirm that I have been adequately informed by the researcher about the nature, conduct, benefits and risks of the study. I have also received, read and understood the above written information. I am aware that the results of the study will be anonymously processed into a research report. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study. I had sufficient opportunity to ask questions and of my own free will declare myself prepared to participate in the study.

Research participant's name: _____

Research participant's signature: _____

Date: _____

Researcher's name: _____

Researcher's signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix D: Permission to conduct research on students

Tshwane University
of Technology

OFFICE OF THE DEPUTY REGISTRAR

14 July 2020

The Research Ethics Committee
Tshwane University of Technology
PRETORIA
0001

RE: REQUEST FOR PERMISSION TO CONDUCT RESEARCH ON STUDENTS

This letter serves to confirm that Mr Simon Thabo Mahlaole, Student number 214001365, has been granted permission to access and collect data at Tshwane University of Technology for post facto research on the:

Project title: The effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intentions at the Tshwane University of Technology.

Faculty: Management Science
Supervisor: Dr Makgabo Justice Malebana

The permission is granted on condition that the research is conducted and results published according to the procedures and methods as approved by the Tshwane University of Technology Research Ethics Committee.

Yours faithfully,

Dr S Poore
Deputy Registrar

•••••
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Office of the Deputy Registrar, Private Bag X680, Pretoria 0001, Tel. 0861 102 422, (+27 12) 382-5130/4421

Website: www.tut.ac.za • e-mail: pooes@tut.ac.za/machethemd@tut.ac.za

Appendix E: Ethical Clearance

Research Ethics Committee

The TUT Research Ethics Committee is a registered Institutional Review Board (IRB 00005968) with the US Office for Human Research Protections (IORG# 0004997) (Expires January 14 2023). Also, it has Federal Wide Assurance for the Protection of Human Subjects for International Institutions (FWA 00011501). In South Africa it is registered with the National Health Research Ethics Council (REC-160509-21).

9 November, 2020

REC Ref #: REC2020-11-010
Name: Mahlaole, ST
Student #: 214001365
Faculty Ref#: FCRE2020/FR/05/001-MS (2)

Mahlaole, ST
C/o Dr MJ Malebane
Department of Management and Entrepreneurship
Faculty of Management Sciences

Dear Mr Mahlaole,

Decision: Final Approval with a Comment

Name: Mahlaole, ST

Project title: *The effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intentions at the Tshwane University of Technology*

Qualification: M Tech: Entrepreneurship (Structured)

Supervisor: Dr MJ Malebane

Co-supervisor: Dr R Küsel

Thank you for submitting the project documents for review by the Research Ethics Committee (REC), Tshwane University of Technology (TUT). In reviewing the documents, the comments and notes below are tabled for your consideration, attention and/or notification:

- **Referral for full REC review**

- The REC took note that the proposal had been referred by the Faculty of Management Sciences [FCRE meeting of August 21, 2020; Reference #: FCRE2020/FR/05/001-MS (2)] to the REC for a full review.

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- The REC received the proposal for inclusion on the agenda of October 26, 2020. The research proposal was reviewed for the first time at the REC meeting on October 26, 2020.

- **Comment**

- The REC expressed concern about the work plan's dates, which suggests that, inter alia, the document (1) would have served at the REC in October/November 2019, and (2) that the final document will be submitted for examination in June 2020.
- The REC requires that the researcher and supervisor adjust the work plan to complete the study in a reasonable timeframe.
- The REC also wishes to emphasise that October 26, 2020 was the first time the study served at the REC.

- **Ethical Approval**

- The REC is satisfied that the ethical concerns related to the study were addressed adequately.
- Final Approval with a Comment is granted to the study.

The Research Ethics Committee, Tshwane University of Technology, reviewed the project documents at its meeting on October 26, 2020. **Final Approval** is granted to the project.

The proposed research project may now continue with the proviso that:

- 1) The researcher/s will conduct the study according to the procedures and methods indicated in the **approved proposal**, particularly in terms of any undertakings and/or assurances made regarding the confidentiality of the collected data.
- 2) The proposal will be submitted to the Committee for prospective ethical clearance if there are any substantial **deviations** and/or changes from the approved proposal.
- 3) The researcher/s will act within the parameters of any applicable **national legislation, professional codes of conduct**, institutional guidelines and scientific standards relevant to the specific field of study. Strict adherence to the following South African legislation, where applicable, is especially important: Protection of Personal Information Act (Act 4 of 2013), Children's Act (Act 38 of 2005) and the National Health Act (Act 61 of 2003).
- 4) The researcher will inform the REC as soon as possible of any **adverse events** involving research participants that may have occurred during the course of the study. It includes the actions and/or processes that were implemented to mitigate and/or prevent any further injuries and/or adverse outcomes.
- 5) The researcher will inform the REC of any **new or unexpected ethical issues** that may have emerged during the course of the study, as well as how these ethical issues were addressed. The researcher must consult with the REC for advice and/or guidance in any such event.
- 6) The current ethics approval expiry date for this project is **November 9, 2022**. No research activities may continue after the ethics approval expiry date. An application for the extension of ethics approval must be submitted for projects that need to continue beyond the expiry date.

Note:

The reference number [top right corner of this communiqué] should be clearly indicated on all forms of communication [e.g. Webmail, E-mail messages, letters] with the intended research participants.

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Yours sincerely,

H Mason (Dr)
Chairperson: Research Ethics Committee
[TUTRef#2020=11=010= MahlaoleST]

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Appendix E: Letters and editing declaration

620 Park Street
Arcadia
0083
Phone: 079 650 2938

20 February 2020

Prof. Liñán Francisco
Universidad de Sevilla
Greater Sevilla Metropolitan Area

Dear Professor Liñán

My name is Simon T. Mahlaole and I am a post graduate student of MTech (Entrepreneurship) from at Tshwane University of Technology writing my dissertation titled, as a study to evaluate the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intention at the Tshwane University of Technology. Under the direction of my supervisor Dr MJ Malebana, Senior Lecturer at the Tshwane University of Technology, who can be reached at email malebanamj@tut.ac.za or contact no +27 83 694 2676. I would like request permission to make use of the Development and cross-cultural application of a specific instrument to measure entrepreneurial intentions (Liñán & Chen, 2009:612) Questionnaire. I would like to use and print your tool under the following conditions:

- I will use the tool only for my research study and will not sell or use it with any compensated or curriculum development activities.
- I will include the copyright statement on all copies of the instrument.
- I will send a copy of my completed research study to your attention upon completion of the study.
- If these are acceptable terms and conditions, please indicate so by replying to me through email: 214001365@tut4life.ac.za or contact +27 79 650 2938

Kind Regards,

Mr Simon Thabo Mahlaole

620 Park Street
Arcadia
0083
Phone: 079 650 2938

13 July 2020

Dr. Solly Pooe,
Deputy Registrar
Tshwane University of Technology
Pretoria West, Staatsartillerie Road
Dear Dr. Pooe

My name is Simon Thabo Mahlaole and I am a registered Master's student in the Department of Management and Entrepreneurship at the Tshwane University of Technology. My supervisor is Dr. Mmakgobo Justice Malebana. The proposed topic of my research is: The effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intentions at the Tshwane University of Technology. The objectives of the study are:

- a) To determine whether entrepreneurship education has a significant relationship with students' entrepreneurial intentions.
- b) To evaluate the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' attitude towards entrepreneurship.
- c) To assess the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' subjective norms.
- d) To determine the effects of entrepreneurship education on students' perceived behavioural control.

I hereby humbly requesting your permission to conduct this study using sample of students from Department of Management and Entrepreneurship in the Faculty of Management Sciences at the Tshwane University of Technology. To assist you in reaching a decision, I have attached to this letter: An information leaflet to give a brief description about nature of this study.

Should you require any further information, please do not hesitate to contact me or my supervisor. Our contact details are as follows:

- Mr. ST Mahlaole can be reached at 0796502938 or e-mail: 214001365@tut4life.ac.za
- Dr. MJ Malebana can be reached at (015) 287 0202 or e-mail: malebanamj@tut.ac.za

Upon completion of the study, I undertake to provide you with a bound copy of the thesis. Your permission to conduct this study on students here at Tshwane University of Technology will be highly appreciated.

Kind Regards,

Mr. Simon Thabo Mahlaole

EDITING DECLARATION

Susanna Elizabeth Louw

Non-accredited member of the South African Translators' Institute
Entry-level member of the Chartered Institute of Editing and Proofreading
Phone 076 588 8561
Email anzelle@wordfix.co.za

DATE: 2021-04-01

I, SE Louw, hereby declare that I did language editing for the dissertation titled ***THE EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION ON STUDENTS' ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS AT THE TSHWANE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY*** by ST Mahlaole, with the exception of images, verbatim quotes and references, and without seeing the final version.

If further information is required, please contact me.

SE Louw

Susanna Elizabeth Louw

2021-04-01

Date